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Foundation of Reasoning through Semantic-empowered Communications: First results

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Abstract

The semantic communication frameworks generally assume that agents share a common ontological language and employ compatible models for semantic extraction and interpretation. Under this assumption, communication errors are typically attributed to lossy semantic compression or incomplete knowledge representation. However, when agents operate with heterogeneous languages or semantic models, communication becomes prone to semantic noise, potentially degrading the performance of communication strategies. Moreover, when communication is instrumental in training the extraction and interpretation models, such a mismatch can contribute to additional model divergence between transmitters and receivers. To mitigate such mismatches, the 6G-GOALS project lays the foundation for next-generation AI-native networks by ensuring efficient, meaningful, and goal-oriented information exchange.

This deliverable presents the foundational efforts of the 6G-GOALS project in addressing semantic mismatches in AI-driven, goal-oriented 6G communication networks. We apply the principles from domain adaptation theory to the mismatch problem between sender(s) and receiver(s) with distinct languages and semantic rules (for instance, when using semantic extraction and interpretation models trained for different domains). Robust JSSC schemes are considered to ensure resilience to model mismatches. Theoretical and algorithmic methods based on optimal transport theory are proposed to identify and implement the set of measurable transport planes over semantic spaces, which enable cost-effective recovery of meaning at the receiver, as intended by the sender. These approaches support the development of goal-oriented communication policies derived from general domain transferability principles. Furthermore, the problem of mismatch in knowledge or beliefs among agents is investigated as an optimal transport problem, drawing connections with domain adaptation, and the intrinsic relationships with rate-distortion theory, which may lead to theoretical guarantees on the existence and achievability of optimal plans, as well as establishing information-theoretic equivalences. Finally, approximate reasoning is explored as a means to relax semantic constraints, enabling flexible interpretation and extended expressiveness in logical representations.

In this document, several advancements are proposed in semantic communication, adaptive encoding and error correction, paving the way for enhanced, reliable AI-driven semantic communications, and driving high-performance, sustainable and reliable 6G systems.

Keywords

Semantic Communication, Semantic mismatch, Semantic channel equalizer, Latent space misalignment, DeepJSSC, Data mismatch, Belief mismatch, Relative representation, Optimal Transport, Knowledge representation.

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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

6G	6th Generation
AF	Attention Feature
AI	Artificial Intelligence
CLIP	Contrastive Language-Image Pretraining
CNN	Convolutional Neural Network
DiT	Diffusion Transformer
DM	Diffusion Model
DNN	Deep Neural Network
E2E	End-to-End
EOT	Entropic Optimal Transport
FID	Frechet Inception Distance
FLOP	Floating-point operation
IB	Information Bottleneck
IoT	Internet of Things
JSCC	Joint Source and Channel Coding
KB	Knowledge Base
KL	Kullback-Leibler
LPIPS	learned Perceptual Image Patch Similarity
MIMO	Multiple-Input Multiple-Output
MuGE	Multi-Granularity Edge Detection
NN	Neural Network
OC-RDF	Output-Constrained Rate-Distortion Function
OT	Optimal Transport
pdf	Probability Density Function
PR	Perfect Realism
PRF	Parseval Reconstruction Formula
PSNR	peak signal-to-noise ratio
RBF	Radial Basis Function
RD	Rate-Distortion
RDP	Rate-Distortion-Perception
RDPF	Rate-Distortion-Perception Function
RR	Relative Representation
RX	Receiver
SemCom	SemCom
SGD	Semantics-Guided Diffusion
SNR	Signal-to-Noise Ratio
TX	Transmitter

1 Introduction

The 6G-GOALS framework integrates communication, computation, control, and intelligence, shifting from traditional data transmission to a goal-oriented and semantic communication (SemCom) paradigm [SDS+24]. To achieve this objective, the 6G-GOALS project seeks to harness the potential of Artificial Intelligence (AI)-native architectures alongside semantic and goal-oriented communication paradigms. It challenges the conventional approach of content-blind transmission paradigm, questioning its relevance for AI processes. Instead of assuming that receivers always benefit from all transmitted data, the 6G-GOALS framework aims to emphasize that information is valuable only when it has practical, exploitable significance for the receiver. The focus on transmitting only the most relevant information is accompanied by the need to ensure alignment with the receiver's specific learning or decision-making needs, as well as on semantic protocols (languages). State-of-the-art (SotA) research on SemCom typically assumes that agents interact using a shared ontology language for knowledge representation, along with compatible semantic extraction (at the transmitter) and interpretation (at the receiver) models. Under this assumption, errors in SemCom are primarily attributed to lossy semantic compression or incomplete knowledge representation. However, when agents rely on different languages and models, communication becomes susceptible to semantic noise. This noise can disrupt optimised coding strategies and lead to significant performance degradation. Furthermore, if communication plays a role in training the extraction and interpretation models, such a mismatch can further exacerbate model divergence between transmitters and receivers.

While conventional communication frameworks focus on preserving signal integrity, goal-driven SemCom extends the efficacy of information exchange beyond the mere transmission of accurate data. A successful communication presupposes a shared understanding of contextual frameworks, communicative intents, and semantic content between the transmitter and the receiver. Nonetheless, when discrepancies exist between their respective internal knowledge representations and reasoning mechanisms, semantic misalignments may arise, leading to semantic distortions, misinterpretations and reduced communication effectiveness.

This deliverable lays the foundation of reasoning of SemCom exploring the impact of different semantic mismatches on communication performance and addressing the derived semantic misalignments. The document presents several advancements with respect to the available SotA in terms of strategies to prevent the disruption of meaning reconstruction, proposing diverse adapted solutions:

- *Data mismatch in Joint Source and Channel Coding (JSCC)*: the contribution explores the advancement of DeepJSCC towards a semantics aligned, high-fidelity transmission approach, proposing a semantic-guided diffusion denoising and a channel denoising adapting to time varying channel conditions.
- *Semantic error detection and correction*: the contribution addresses the detection and correction discrepancies between transmitted and received meanings in SemCom. The proposed solution mitigates semantic errors under various conditions, including adversarial attacks, input feature changes, physical channel variations, and user preference shifts.
- *Language mismatch*: the proposed pragmatic goal-oriented communication formalizes the process of aligning communicative intent with practical task execution. The contribution addresses language mismatches to mitigate the consequent semantic noise, leading to interpretation errors.
- *Semantic channel equalization*: this technique addresses the semantic mismatch raised when independently trained encoders and decoders use different representations by partitioning the semantic space into distinct atoms and aligning the latent spaces of the

mismatched encoders and decoders. This deliverable proposes three different solutions to handle this particular mismatch:

- A soft partitioning of the latent space, which captures richer semantic meaning and consequently enhances the performance of the equalizer, while enabling robust communication in dynamic multi-agent settings (e.g., autonomous driving or drone swarm coordination).
- A relative representation (RR) method framed within the general context of frame theory, considers signal expansion and compression, giving additional flexibility to the communication system.
- A semantic equalization framework based on RRs that does not need any re-training and requires sharing a small amount of data between transmitter and receiver, allowing different models to communicate by projecting their semantic representations into a shared space.
- *Latent space alignment*: a Multiple-Input Multiple-Output (MIMO)-based integration into the semantic channel equalization scheme is proposed as solution to mitigate the semantic noise generated from heterogeneous encoding schemes.
- *Goal/belief mismatch*: two final contributions address the semantic mismatch occurring when the information exchange does not rely on a common goal, belief and context between communication entities. First, Optimal Transport (OT) theory is used to address mismatches in common background knowledge leveraging domain adaptation techniques, second, Rate-Distortion-Perception (RDP) theory is integrated to optimize communication strategies for knowledge alignment.

1.1 Taxonomy of Semantic Mismatch

This section describes the three principal different semantic mismatches addressed along the deliverable. At the end, a taxonomy table is proposed together with the correspondent references for contributions.

1.1.1 Data mismatch for JSCC

A DeepJSCC model trained on high-resolution natural images (e.g., landscapes, human faces) might struggle when transmitting medical scans, sketches, or synthetic images, as these have vastly different statistical properties. This issue is particularly problematic when the trained model is expected to generalize across diverse datasets, such as handling both real-world photographs and cartoon-style images. The learned feature space of the DeepJSCC encoder is biased toward the training data distribution, which may lead to poor feature representation for unseen input styles, especially ML-driven SemCom trained on a limited dataset. Consequently, even if the channel conditions remain the same, the decoder might struggle to reconstruct images that were not well-represented in the training set, leading to degraded perceptual quality, colour shifts, or missing structural details in the reconstructed images. A detailed contribution on this specific semantic mismatch can be found in Section 3.

1.1.2 Language mismatch

In the context of SemCom, intelligent agents require reliable exchange of semantics to enable effective cooperation. One of the major challenges to system reliability is the semantic noise arising from semantic discrepancies in how meaning is interpreted or reconstructed. This semantic mismatch arises from divergent methods of logic, interpretation, or knowledge among different devices, leading to latent space misalignment between transmitted and received meanings.

Within the semantic mismatch, we can identify a specific *Language Mismatch*, occurring in SemCom when intelligent agents interact on different languages, causing interpretation errors and defective cooperative strategies. The communication reliability relies on common or shared language (either natural or artificial), which endows messages with semantic meanings, and which can be learned a priori e.g., via a learning procedure, or from an interactive consensus by learning a communication protocol.

In AI-driven SemCom, the involved agents exchange meaningful representations of data, processed using independently trained models, and develop unique semantic languages, leading to mismatches that hinder effective communication. *Semantic channel equalization* aims to minimize semantic noise during communication, avoiding retraining or extensive data exchange.

A detailed contribution on language mismatch can be found in Section 4.

1.1.3 Goal/belief Mismatch

In goal-oriented SemCom, effective information exchange necessitates a mutual understanding of context, objectives, and intended meaning between the transmitter and receiver. However, when their internal knowledge representations and reasoning models are misaligned, belief mismatches arise, distorting interpretation and degrading communication effectiveness. The mismatch occurs when communication participants have differing objectives or underlying beliefs about the transmitted information, leading to misinterpretation or suboptimal decision-making. This can arise due to variations in prior knowledge, domain adaptation challenges, or conflicting intentions in goal-oriented communication. The proposed solutions addressing this semantic mismatch are detailed in Section 5.

Table 1 Taxonomy table for Semantic Mismatches

Semantic Mismatch	Contribution
Data mismatch	Section 3.1 Denoising diffusion models based JSCC robustness design for image transmission.
Language mismatch	Section 4.1 Semantic error detection and correction. Section 4.2 Pragmatic goal-oriented communication. Section 4.3 Soft partitioning of latent space for semantic channel equalization. Section 4.4.1 Trade-off of compression and space alignment in goal-oriented semantic communication via relative representation. Section 4.4.2 Semantic channel equalization via relative representation. Section 4.5 Latent Space Alignment for AI-Native MIMO semantic communications.
Goal/belief mismatch	Section 5.1 Belief mismatch and semantic alignment using optimal transport. Section 5.2 On the intersection of optimal transport, rate-distortion-perception theory: a new promising solution.

1.2 Structure of the document

The deliverable is structured as follows. Section 2 introduces the main three theoretical frameworks leveraged by the proposed solutions to mitigate the SemCom mismatches. In Section 3 data mismatch is addressed with DeepJSCC methods. The semantic mismatch is the topic of Section 4, where different AI-based techniques are proposed to mitigate different semantic misalignments. Finally, Section 5 addresses the goal/belief mismatch, leveraging optimal transport and rate-distortion-perception theory.

2 Theoretical framework

This section presents the core theoretical foundations underpinning the proposed methodologies in this deliverable, focusing on three key concepts: *Optimal Transport*, *Deep Joint-Source Channel Coding*, and *Relative Representation*. OT provides a framework to optimize the transmission and reconstruction of data by aligning semantic-aware encoding and decoding processes. Deep JSCC unifies source coding and channel coding into an end-to-end (E2E) learnable system, ensuring robust performance under challenging network conditions. Lastly, RR enables flexible unification of different latent representations without the need for retraining, thus facilitating modular and adaptive communication approaches.

The subsections that follow delve deeper into each concept and explain how they interrelate with our proposed methodologies.

2.1 Optimal transport theory

Optimal Transport (OT) theory provides a mathematical framework for measuring and optimizing the transfer of probability distributions. Originally introduced by Monge [M81] and later reformulated by Kantorovich [K58], OT has become a fundamental tool in diverse fields such as economics, fluid mechanics, and, more recently, machine learning and communication systems. The central idea of OT is to determine the most efficient way to transport mass from one distribution to another while minimizing a given cost function. This concept has been widely studied and extended, leading to the development of computational methods that enable its practical use in high-dimensional settings [V08].

In SemCom, OT has emerged as a powerful tool for aligning mismatched knowledge representations between the transmitter and receiver. Unlike traditional communication systems that focus on minimizing symbol-level distortions, OT operates at the distributional level, allowing for a more holistic approach to reducing semantic discrepancies. By leveraging OT-based methods, it is possible to quantify and mitigate knowledge mismatches arising from variations in prior information, different training datasets, or domain shifts. This makes OT particularly useful in goal-oriented communication scenarios, where the objective is not only to transmit data accurately but also to preserve the intended meaning [PC19].

Despite its theoretical elegance, classical OT formulations suffer from high computational complexity, making them challenging to deploy in real-time communication environments. The computation of the Wasserstein distance, a key metric in OT, involves solving a linear programming problem with cubic complexity, which becomes infeasible for large-scale applications [V08]. To address this, several regularization techniques, such as entropy-regularized OT [C13], have been proposed to improve computational efficiency while maintaining the accuracy of transport-based alignment. These advancements have led to practical implementations of OT in deep learning, generative modelling, and domain adaptation [GPC18, MLS+20], all of which are closely related to SemCom.

Recent research has explored the integration of OT with machine learning models to enable adaptive and robust transmission strategies. In particular, OT-based methods have been applied to align latent space representations in neural networks (NNs) [ACB17] optimize generative models, and improve transfer learning across different domains [CFH+17, RCF+19] These

developments provide a strong foundation for extending OT to semantic-aware communication, where it can be used to optimize the transmission of meaningful information in dynamic and resource-constrained environments. By incorporating OT into SemCom frameworks, it is possible to achieve more efficient knowledge transfer, reduce semantic noise, and enhance goal-oriented decision-making [SCK+21]. The contributions related to OT in SemCom are presented in Sections 5.1 and 5.2.

2.2 Deep Joint Source Channel Coding (JSCC)

A traditional approach, inspired by Shannon’s separation theorem, involves designing source and channel coding independently. However, this method is theoretically optimal in the asymptotic case of infinite block length for ergodic source and channel distributions [CT91]. In practical scenarios with finite block lengths, especially relevant in emerging applications like the Internet of Things (IoT) and edge intelligence, the separation-based approach is known to be suboptimal.

Despite its advantages, developing practical JSCC schemes has remained a longstanding challenge. Most existing research on JSCC either focuses on theoretical models, such as Gaussian or Gauss-Markov sources [HFR09] [AFC+14], or optimizes parameters of separate source and channel codes [PHC00] [PWB+07]. A key limitation has been the lack of practical JSCC schemes and theoretical performance bounds for lossy JSCC in finite block lengths, particularly when dealing with real-world sources like images.

Recently, however, significant advancements have been made in Deep JSCC, driven by the adoption of Deep Neural Networks (DNNs) [BBG19] [YBK22] [WSB+24] [ETD+23]. These models enable direct mapping of input source signals to channel symbols and their reconstruction at the decoder, offering promising alternatives to traditional methods.

Figure 2-1 The diagram of conventional separate source-channel coding scheme (a) and the novel JSCC (b).

Deep JSCC uses a single, end-to-end neural network to directly map input, for example, image pixels, to complex-valued channel inputs, learning both compression and protection against transmission errors simultaneously, shown in Figure 2-1(b). By treating the entire transmission as a learning problem, it creates robust, adaptive, and efficient end-to-end systems that are particularly powerful for low Signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) channel condition compared to the separate scheme.

Figure 2-2 illustrates a representative of the encoder and decoder architectures used for implementing image transmission by the proposed deep JSCC scheme. At the encoder side, it begins by normalizing input images, scaling pixel values between 0 and 1. It consists of five convolutional layers, each followed by PReLU activation functions, which help in learning complex features. The final convolutional layer outputs a latent vector, which is then processed by a normalization layer to enforce an average power constraint on the transmitted signal. The resulting encoded representation is a complex-valued signal, ready for transmission over the communication channel. At the decoder side, the decoder performs the inverse operations to the encoder. It starts by mapping the real and imaginary parts of the received complex-valued noisy channel outputs into real values. These values are passed through a series of transpose convolutional layers, which progressively transform and upsample the features to restore the image. The architecture mirrors the encoder in terms of hyperparameters, with PReLU activation functions applied to all but the final layer. The last layer utilizes a sigmoid activation function to ensure output values remain within the [0, 1] range. Finally, a denormalization layer scales the output by 255, producing reconstructed pixel values in the [0, 255] range.

Figure 2-2 A representative of encoder and decoder neural network architectures used in the implementation of the deep JSCC scheme

Mathematically, the encoder process or function can be parameterized using a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) with parameters. Let \tilde{z} and x denotes the output of encoder and input of encoder, respectively. Then, we have this relationship

$$\tilde{z} = f_{\theta}(x),$$

where θ stands for the neural network parameters. Followed by power normalization layer, we have

$$z = \sqrt{P} \frac{\tilde{z}}{\sqrt{\tilde{z}\tilde{z}^*}},$$

where P stands for the transmit power. At the decoder side, the signal z passes through wireless channel, denoted by h , we have

$$y = hz + n,$$

where n is the receive noise. The decoder maps the noisy complex-valued signal y to an estimation of the original input x using a decoding function $g_{\phi}(\cdot)$, where the decoding function is parametrised by the decoder CNN with parameter set ϕ , namely

$$\tilde{x} = g_{\phi}(y).$$

The encoding and decoding functions are designed jointly to minimize the average distortion between the original input image x and its reconstruction \tilde{x} produced by the decoder:

$$\tilde{x}(\theta^*, \phi^*) = \min_{\theta, \phi} E(d(x, \tilde{x})),$$

where $d(x, \tilde{x})$ is a given distortion measure. Although the true distribution of the input data $p(x)$ is often unknown, we can approximate the expected distribution by sampling from an available dataset. Further details on this work can be found in Section 3.1.

2.3 Relative representation

In modern machine learning, diverse encoding functions often map the same input data into distinct latent spaces. This phenomenon can be problematic in multi-agent scenarios, where aligning representations for downstream tasks becomes challenging. Relative Representations (RRs) [MMF+22] address this issue by projecting each latent space onto a shared coordinate system defined by a set of anchor points. This projection measures how similar data points are to the anchors, allowing modules to be 'stitched' together without further optimization steps (i.e., zero-shot stitching), provided they share the same underlying data semantics.

Figure 2-3 Visualization illustrating how two latent spaces—obtained from two independently trained encoding functions (NNs) on the CIFAR10 dataset—can be projected into a unified space through relative representation.

Consider two encoding functions, each trained on the same dataset \mathcal{X} , that map an input signal to a lower-dimensional latent space:

$$E_{\theta}: \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^d, \quad E_{\psi}: \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^b.$$

We denote the latent space of each map as $\mathcal{X}_{(\cdot)}$. Specifically, \mathcal{X}_{θ} and \mathcal{X}_{ψ} represent the sets of absolute representations, i.e., the outputs of E_{θ} and E_{ψ} , respectively. The goal of RRs is to map both \mathcal{X}_{θ} and \mathcal{X}_{ψ} into a unified space \mathcal{R} . For a generic latent space $\mathcal{X}_{(\cdot)}$, [MMF+22] defines:

$$\mathcal{R}_{\mathcal{X}}(\mathbf{x}, \mathcal{A}, d) = [d(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{a}_1), \dots, d(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{a}_{|\mathcal{A}|})],$$

where the latent vector $\mathbf{x} \in \mathcal{X}_{(\cdot)}$ corresponds to a sample $s \in \mathcal{X}$. Here, \mathcal{A} is the anchor matrix whose columns are vectors obtained from the encoding of a fixed set of samples, i.e., the *anchor set*. The function d is a similarity function, e.g., cosine similarity. When the same RR transformation is applied to both \mathcal{X}_{θ} and \mathcal{X}_{ψ} , it results in $T_{\theta}(\mathcal{X}_{\theta}) \approx T_{\psi}(\mathcal{X}_{\psi})$, where $T_{\theta}: \mathcal{X}_{\theta} \rightarrow \mathcal{R}$ and $T_{\psi}: \mathcal{X}_{\psi} \rightarrow \mathcal{R}$. Then a relative decoder

$$D: \mathcal{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{|\mathcal{T}|},$$

is trained to perform a downstream task \mathcal{T} enabling zero-shot module stitching. The key assumption from [MMF+22] is that the transformations T preserve the angles between elements of the latent space:

$$\angle(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) = \angle(T\mathbf{x}, T\mathbf{y}), \quad \forall (\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) \in \mathcal{X}_{(\cdot)}.$$

This indicates that data are predominantly characterized by the angles between vectors. Consequently, distinct latent spaces that encode the same semantic content can be related through an isometric transformation.

The effectiveness of RRs for unifying representations has been demonstrated for both text and image data [MMF+22] and for reinforcement learning problems [RMM+24]. Multiple metrics to compute the similarity score have also been explored [CMF+23], and their generalization capabilities have been showcased [NFM+23]. Moreover, [FBC+24] introduces an optimisation strategy that leverages RRs to dynamically optimize communication, computation, and learning resources, such as anchor sets and encoders. This approach aims to enable energy-efficient, low-latency, and effective SemCom. However, all these works assume it is possible to train a relative decoder in the new representation space, which may be infeasible in resource-constrained networks.

To overcome this issue, in [MMF+24], [HFS+24], [FBC+25], it was demonstrated how to recover the original absolute representation, eliminating the need for a relative decoder. Specifically, [MMF+24] employs the pseudo-inverse of the anchor matrix to recover the absolute representation, whereas [HFS+24] uses a sample-efficient optimisation algorithm to achieve the same goal, thereby generalizing semantic channel equalization to arbitrary similarity functions. Lastly, [FBC+25] proposes a frame-based approach that stabilizes and simplifies the methodology initially presented in [MMF+24]. Further details on these works can be found in Section 4.4.

3 Data mismatch

This section presents the method to address the data mismatch issue in DeepJSCC explored in this deliverable, focusing on the new techniques and model architecture to design robust image transmission over the wireless channel. We first revisit the classic DeepJSCC and introduce the Diffusion Models (DMs) and refinement mechanisms. In addition, semantics guidance (such as text descriptions or edge maps) is also provided, which further enhances the robustness of image transmission when the source distribution varies.

3.1 Denoising diffusion models based JSCC robustness design for image transmission

Context and motivation

In DeepJSCC, the encoder maps images directly into channel symbols, and the decoder reconstructs the images from noisy channel outputs. Unlike traditional separation-based coding schemes, DeepJSCC optimizes this mapping in an end-to-end manner using DNNs as show in Figure 3-1(a). However, a fundamental data mismatch can arise due to the variability in input source distributions. The learned feature space of the DeepJSCC encoder is biased toward the training data distribution, which may lead to poor feature representation for unseen input styles. Consequently, even if the channel conditions remain the same, the decoder might struggle to reconstruct images that are not well-represented in the training set, leading to degraded perceptual quality, color shifts, or missing structural details in the reconstructed images.

In this section, to address this input source mismatch, we introduce DM as a robust denoising and refinement mechanism [ZWZ+24]. DMs have the ability to learn a wide distribution of natural images and iteratively refine noisy or distorted representations toward a more accurate and perceptually meaningful reconstruction. By incorporating a semantics-guided DM into DeepJSCC, we ensure that even if the transmitted image features come from an unseen distribution, the DM can leverage its learned priors to enhance missing details and restore image fidelity. Additionally, the semantics guidance (such as text descriptions or edge maps) provides contextual constraints, allowing the diffusion process to align the reconstruction with the intended semantic content rather than blindly restoring arbitrary image features. This integration significantly improves generalization across different input distributions, allowing the DeepJSCC framework to handle diverse image types with higher robustness and perceptual consistency.

The contribution of this work is three-fold: (1) It integrates DM into DeepJSCC to counteract data mismatch to improve wireless image transmission; (2) A novel diffusion-based denoising approach for wireless channels is proposed; (3) Semantics-Guided Diffusion (SGD)-JSCC introduces a pilot-free step-matching mechanism, where the diffusion model adapts to channel conditions dynamically by estimating SNR directly from the received signal. This reduces overhead and simplifies deployment in low-latency settings where explicit pilots are costly.

(a) Standard DeepJSCC scheme.

(b) Proposed semantics guided DeepJSCC scheme.

Figure 3-1: Different DeepJSCC transmission paradigms

System model and problem statement

As shown in Figure 3-1(b), the proposed SGD-JSCC schemes mainly consists of a DeepJSCC encoder, semantic extractor & semantic side information encoder, wireless channel, diffusion denoiser, semantic side information decoder, and DeepJSCC decoder.

At the transmitter side, the transmitter encodes the input image x into a latent feature representation f using a DeepJSCC encoder:

$$f = F(x; \theta),$$

where θ represents the trainable parameters of the encoder (Figure 2-1(b)). A semantic extractor is employed at the encoder to directly extract the semantic features of x , yielding s . The exact form of s is flexible and can be customized at the transmitter for a specific semantic quality metric. Then, s is subsequently encoded into its latent representation, leading to:

$$o = H(s),$$

where $H(\cdot)$ denotes the encoding function of s . Then, f and o are concatenated to form z as the channel input.

At the receiver side, the receiver obtains the noisy channel output y after the transmitter sends z over the wireless channel. We apply minimum mean square error (MMSE) channel equalisation to balance channel distortion and noise, resulting in the equalized channel output:

$$y_{eq} = \frac{h^*}{|h|^2 + \sigma^2} y,$$

where h denotes the wireless channel, σ^2 is the noise power. Thus, the estimation of z is y_{eq} . Then, the receiver reconstructs the semantic side information, as follows:

$$\tilde{s} = G(\tilde{o}),$$

where \tilde{o} is the received latent features of the semantics s and G denotes the decoding function. We consider employing DM to pre-process the noisy feature \tilde{f} (\tilde{f} is the received latent features of the image x) under the guidance of \tilde{s} . The denoising process is given as follows:

$$\hat{f} = D(\tilde{f}|\tilde{s}, \Omega),$$

where D and Ω are the trainable parameters in DM and the denoising operation, respectively. Finally, the denoised feature \hat{f} is fed into the JSCC decoder to reconstruct the image:

$$\hat{x} = G(\hat{f}; \Psi),$$

where Ψ and G are the trainable parameters in DeepJSCC decoder and the decoding function, respectively.

Proposed SGD-JSCC architecture

This subsection presents a pipeline of the SGD-JSCC architecture to enable efficient image transmission as shown in Figure 3-1(b). In the following, we detail the pipeline of SGD-JSCC in four main modules: DeepJSCC encoder, semantic extractor & semantic side information encoder, diffusion denoiser and DeepJSCC decoder.

Figure 3-2: Architecture of the DeepJSCC

DeepJSCC encoder

The architecture of the DeepJSCC is depicted in the upper of Figure 3-2, where residual blocks are utilized as the basic feature extraction modules. Additionally, a self-attention module is incorporated after each residual block to further enhance representation and reconstruction capabilities of the DeepJSCC model. Within each self-attention module, three convolutional layers are employed to obtain the query, key, and value sequences from the corresponding intermediate feature map, which are subsequently processed through the self-attention mechanism.

Semantic extractor & semantic side information encoder

To facilitate the reliable transmission of critical semantic information, we explore two types of semantic guidance: text descriptions, which convey coarse semantic information, and edge maps, which offer finer semantic details.

Coarse Semantics: Text Description. In human-level communication, we can often imagine a reasonable reconstruction of an image based on the descriptions provided by other people. Inspired by this, text descriptions serve as suitable semantic guidance that encapsulate the general information behind images. We use Bootstrapped Language-Image Pretraining 2 (BLIP2) [LLS+23], an off-the-shelf state-of-the-art image captioning model, to extract the text descriptions for the input images. The transmission cost of text descriptions is negligible compared to that of images. Therefore, we neglect the transmission cost of text and assume the text description can be transmitted to the receiver perfectly.

Figure 3-3 DeepJSCC transmission for the image edge map

Fine Semantics: Edge Map. Text descriptions provide lightweight semantics but only allow for coarse guidance during the denoising process. To address this limitation, we explore the use of edge maps as an additional semantic guidance with structural details. An edge map is a gray-scale image that highlights the edges of objects in an image. We use Multi-Granularity Edge Detection (MuGE), a deep learning-based edge extractor, to extract edge information from input images as shown in Figure 3-3.

Diffusion denoiser

It leverages a Diffusion Transformer (DiT) model, enhanced with semantics-guided denoising mechanisms, such as text and edge map guidance. The architecture consists of several key components: DiT Model, semantics-guided controlNet Module, and pilot-free step matching for noise estimation, and is based on two types of semantic guidance: text descriptions and edge maps. The different diffusion denoiser modules are shown in Figure 3-4 and Figure 3-5, respectively.

Figure 3-4 Network architecture of DiT model for text description case

Figure 3-5 Network architecture of DiT model for edge map case

DeepJSCC decoder

The DeepJSCC decoder is shown in the bottom of Figure 3-2, and it takes the denoised feature representation from the diffusion denoiser and uses it to reconstruct the image as accurately as possible. The key components of the DeepJSCC decoder include residual blocks, self-attention layer, Conv2d, and power normalization layer.

Training strategy

The proposed SGD-JSCC scheme is trained in three stages. In the first stage, the JSCC encoder and decoder are jointly trained based on the Imagenet dataset under a fixed channel setting (AWGN channel with SNR=10dB in the simulations). In the second stage, we train the text-guided DM. We collect approximately 14 million text-image pairs from various open datasets, including SA-1B, JourneyDB, CC3M, Datacomp, and CelebA-HQ. With this diverse dataset, our DM is capable of understanding open-domain text descriptions and generating the corresponding visual data. All the images are center-cropped and resized to 128 × 128. In the third stage, we incorporate edge maps as structural guidance for the well-trained text-guided DM obtained from stage two.

Simulation Results

In the following, the simulation results are provided. We adopt the COCO2017 dataset [LMB+14] for evaluation and use the Imagenet dataset [DDS+09] for training the DM used in the DeepJSCC-Diff scheme. For DeepJSCC and DeepJSCCDiff, the COCO training set is used for training the JSCC models.

The following benchmark schemes are considered:

- SGD-JSCC: the proposed scheme.
- ADJSCC: the ADJSCC scheme refers to the DeepJSCC architecture in, which iteratively downsamples and upsamples image data using residual and attention blocks. The Attention Feature (AF) modules are integrated after each upsample block to incorporate SNR information into the DeepJSCC network.
- DeepJSCC-Diff: a diffusion-based scheme aimed at improving the perceptual performance of DeepJSCC through post-processing.
- JSCCformer: it refers to the JSCC architecture with vision transformer, which can also achieve SNR-adaptivity using a single model.
- VAEJSCC: a variation of the proposed SGDJSCC scheme that does not use diffusion for denoising. VAEJSCC serves as a baseline to validate the effectiveness of our semantic-guided DM.

In addition, the following performance metrics are considered:

- PSNR (peak signal-to-noise ratio): it measures the similarity between two images based on pixel intensity differences.
- LPIPS (Learned perceptual Image Patch Similarity): it measures perceptual similarity between images using deep features.
- CLIP (Contrastive Language-Image Pretraining): the CLIP score measures the similarity between image and text descriptions.
- FID (Fréchet inception distance): it assesses visual quality by calculating the statistical similarity between the original image set and the reconstructed image set.

In Figure 3-6, we compare the proposed scheme with three benchmarks. First, it can be observed that the ADJSCC scheme has better PSNR performance. The proposed SGD-JSCC scheme improves the PSNR performance compared to VAEJSCC, with a gap of only 2.5dB

compared to the state-of-the-art JSCC scheme. Second, in terms of LPIPS metric, the proposed SGD-JSCC scheme outperforms both the ADJSCC and JSCCformer schemes. It also achieves much better performance than VAEJSCC when $\text{SNR} \leq 5$ dB, validating the effectiveness of the semantics-guided DM in denoising. Third, generative models are naturally beneficial for improving perceptual performance, as measured by CLIP score and FID shown in Figure 3-6(c) and Figure 3-6(d).

Figure 3-6 Average reconstruction quality comparison under different measures when CSI is available at the receiver.

The DeepJSCC-Diff scheme aims to first reconstruct a lower-resolution image, followed by a super-resolution process using DM. This approach results in better perceptual performance in the low SNR regime (i.e., $\text{SNR} \leq 5$ dB) compared to ADJSCC, especially in terms of the FID metric. However, the performance of DeepJSCC-Diff is limited by the imperfect transmission of the lower-resolution image and also constrained by the introduced irreversible downsampling operation. As a result, a performance floor occurs when $\text{SNR} > 5$ dB. In contrast, by transforming the paradigm from post-processing the DeepJSCC output into preprocessing the channel output, the proposed SGD-JSCC scheme benefits from dynamically translating the SNR to a specific intermediate state of diffusion process. SGD-JSCC significantly improves the perceptual quality of VAEJSCC in low SNR regime and retains performance in the high SNR regime. Moreover, by embracing semantics guidance and open-world text-image datasets, SGD-JSCC outperforms the DeepJSCC-Diff in terms of both reconstruction and perceptual performance. The demonstrated improvements highlight the superiority of the proposed SGD-JSCC scheme.

Figure 3-7 Average reconstruction quality comparison when CSI is unknown at neither the transmitter nor the receiver.

In Figure 3-7, we consider the scenario where neither the transmitter nor the receiver has access to CSI. In this case, the AF modules in the JSCC models of both the ADJSCC and DeepJSCC-Diff schemes are removed, leading to a performance drop compared to the corresponding setups with CSI available at both ends. Interestingly, the performance of the proposed SGD-JSCC method remains nearly identical, whether the SNR is available or not. This robustness arises because our scheme does not require CSI at the transmitter for adaptive design. Furthermore, it bypasses the need for precise SNR information by directly estimating it from the noisy JSCC features (channel output) and leveraging this estimate for step matching in the diffusion denoising process. This indicates that the proposed scheme is a promising solution in scenarios where CSI is unavailable or challenging to measure accurately.

Conclusions

We proposed a novel semantics-guided diffusion DeepJSCC scheme, called SGD-JSCC. First, we explored different types of semantics and their corresponding transmission schemes. Then, we designed a DiT model for channel denoising, supporting both text and edge map guidance by integrating a cross-attention mechanism and ControlNet architecture. We made necessary modifications to the original DM and trained it from scratch to seamlessly integrate with DeepJSCC. The proposed method addressed key challenges in DeepJSCC, including data mismatch, noise-induced distortions, and adaptability to varying channel conditions, by leveraging semantic side information (text and edge maps) and a diffusion-based denoising mechanism.

4 Language mismatch

In the context of SemCom, intelligent agents require reliable exchange of semantics to enable effective cooperation [SC22]. This is possible thanks to a common or shared language (either natural or artificial), which endows messages with semantic meanings. Common language can be learned a priori e.g., via a learning procedure or it can emerge from an interactive consensus by learning a communication protocol. Alternatively, common language can be suggested by the environment, where agents ground their language in representations of the observed world.

Current work on SemCom often assumes that the interaction between agents is based on an agreed common language, possibly learned or given [SC23]. This assumption considers that communication errors occur only because of i) syntactic wireless channel, ii) lossy semantic compression, or iii) limited expressivity of semantic extraction and interpretation function, ruling how knowledge is extracted, represented and interpreted. However, when agents use distinct languages, it has been shown that communication is prone to semantic noise that might stimulate interpretation errors causing defective cooperation strategies [SC22].

This section focuses on how to deal with agents that use different languages, since there is a risk of semantic noise leading to misinterpretations and defective cooperation. To address the issue of latent space misalignment, i.e., semantic noise stemming from heterogeneous encoding schemes, different novel AI-driven contributions are proposed:

- The detection and correction of semantic errors.
- Estimation of the semantic and effectiveness mismatches due to the misalignment.
- Semantic channel equalization to align latent representations.
- Applications of relative representations to the semantic channel equalization problem.
- Semantic channel equalization for MIMO channels.

4.1 Semantic error detection and correction

Context and motivation

Error detection and correction are essential for ensuring robust and reliable operation in modern communication systems, particularly in complex transmission environments. However, discussions on these topics have largely been overlooked in SemCom, which focuses on transmitting meaning rather than symbols, leading to significant improvements in communication efficiency. Despite these advantages, semantic errors-stemming from discrepancies between transmitted and received meanings-present a major challenge to system reliability. The work exposed in this section, and detailed in [LLA24], addresses this gap by proposing a comprehensive framework for detecting and correcting semantic errors in SemCom systems. We formally define semantic error, detection, and correction mechanisms, and identify key sources of semantic errors. To address these challenges, we develop a Gaussian process (GP)-based method for latent space monitoring to detect errors, alongside a human-in-the-loop reinforcement learning (HITL-RL) [RDW+24] approach to optimize semantic model configurations using user feedback.

Experimental results validate the effectiveness of the proposed methods in mitigating semantic errors under various conditions, including adversarial attacks, input feature changes, physical channel variations, and user preference shifts. This work lays the foundation for more reliable and adaptive SemCom systems with robust semantic error management techniques.

System model and problem statement

Despite extensive research focused on SemCom, most existing literature assumes that SemCom system is primarily unidirectional without either the error handling ability or a control loop with feedback. The semantic error, defined as the discrepancy between the transmitted and recovered information, has received less attention. Unlike physical and medium access control (MAC) layers, where techniques such as forward error correction (FEC) and automatic repeat request (ARQ) are proposed for reliable data transmission, the virtual semantic layer lacks a robust error management strategy.

We believe detecting and correcting semantic errors are crucial in a SemCom system for several reasons: (1) the detection and correction processes preserve the intended meaning by ensuring that the sender's message is accurately conveyed, maintaining contextual accuracy to prevent misinterpretation of context-sensitive information; (2) these mechanisms optimize resource utilization by focusing on transmitting meaning rather than ensuring perfect data accuracy; (3) they enhance human-machine interaction by enabling systems to better understand user intent, even in the presence of input imperfections; and (4) robust communication is ensured by providing resilience against noise and distortions that could compromise the conveyed meaning. While previous studies have explored semantic error detection and correction, they primarily address mismatches at the terminal level without incorporating autonomous intelligence. A comprehensive framework for intelligent semantic error detection and correction applicable across the semantic channel remains absent.

We begin by defining the concepts of semantic error, along with semantic error detection and correction. We then identify the potential root causes of semantic errors within the SemCom framework and outline corresponding solutions for addressing them.

- *Semantic Error*: a discrepancy between the transmitted raw information and the recovered information at the receiver in a goal-oriented SemCom system.
- *Semantic Error Detection*: the process of identifying semantic errors.
- *Semantic Error Correction*: the process of correcting the transmitted semantic information according to the results of semantic error detection.

An illustration of the semantic error is shown in Figure 4-1. Semantic errors primarily arise from a mismatch or misalignment between the prior domain knowledge embedded in the SemCom encoder/decoder and the new execution domain. The causes of this mismatch are varied, including:

- a) **Input feature change**: This refers to the statistical properties of the input feature used to the ML-based semantic models changing over time. It is a significant challenge for SemCom models when the distribution of the feature in the inference stage is different from the prior knowledge learned from the training feature.
- b) **Channel noise and changes**: The SemCom model's performance deteriorates when the channel property changes significantly. That is because current SemCom models usually adopt the JSCC scheme to improve transmission efficiency. That is to say that the channel's prosperity was mesmerized by the SemCom encoder, so the obvious channel changes might lead to the malfunction of the encoder, and introduce the semantic error.
- c) **Adversarial attack targeting the NN-based encoder and decoder**: With adversarial attacks, carefully crafted imperceptible perturbations can be added to the input data of SemCom

models. That can mislead the semantic NN into making incorrect predictions, which in turn, generates the semantic error [GSS14].

- d) User changes: User preferences and tastes often change over time or differ across individuals. A static SemCom model cannot adapt to these variations, resulting in semantic errors from users' subjective perspectives.

The first three factors are closely intertwined with the data and model, while the final factor is more subjective. Therefore, semantic error detection should employ distinct methods tailored to each specific factor.

Figure 4-1: An illustration of the semantic error

Proposed methodology and solution

As SemCom sees broader use, semantic errors are likely to occur frequently, especially when encountering the factors mentioned above. Consequently, we believe that semantic error detection and correlation should serve as a core mechanism within the SemCom framework, enhancing its robustness in dynamic environments and with diverse users, ensuring correct and satisfactory operation.

Within current SemCom concepts, semantic information is considered a compact representation of raw data, with its precise measurements or meanings being agnostic. This presents significant challenges for detecting and correcting semantic errors, as these errors cannot be easily identified through quantitative metrics at the receiver.

Hence, in this work, we propose two novel methods for semantic error detection, respectively, that is:

- *Leveraging the data distribution on the latent space.* The latent space of the SemCom model represents the compressed input data distribution. Compared with the raw input data, the dimension of the latent space is usually small and compact. The input distribution changes can be directly reflected in the latent space. Thus, the monitoring of the latent space distribution is a valuable way to identify the semantic error. Especially considering the exception of a communication system of introducing less overhead, the monitoring of the encoded data either in the sender or receiver is more practical and communication effective.
- *Through the UE's collective feedback collection.* This is particularly raised for the semantic unsatisfactory caused by the UE's change, due to differences in geography, culture, and taste. In this case, the performance of SemCom is determined by the UE's subjective feeling. Therefore, we propose to collect feedback from UEs to help the performance evaluation of SemCom models. For instance, semantic errors that trigger negative responses from users can be detected. Inspired by the concept of HITL-RL, we propose the HITL-RL SemCom method for semantic error detection correction.

The semantic error correction process will then utilize the results from semantic error detection to update both the knowledge base (KB) and the semantic model accordingly.

Distribution deviation identification with Gaussian processes

As mentioned in the previous section, semantic errors can be identified by monitoring the latent space within the SemCom framework. The goal is to detect anomaly points in the latent space that indicate significant deviations from the learned data distribution. To effectively capture the complex, non-linear relationships in the latent space and account for uncertainty, we propose using GPs. GPs offer a probabilistic approach to modelling latent space distributions and quantifying uncertainty, making them useful for identifying outliers and anomalies. Figure 4-2 illustrates the latent vector monitoring process using GP for the SemCom framework.

Figure 4-2: Latent vector monitoring with GP for semantic error detection

The GP provides a non-parametric way to model the distribution of latent variables, capturing complex relationships in the data while offering uncertainty estimates. This is particularly useful for tasks like anomaly detection in the latent space, where the GP’s predictive uncertainty helps identify points that deviate from the expected behaviour.

For a test point z_* , the GP provides a posterior predictive distribution:

$$p(f(z_*) | Z, f(Z)) = N(\mu(z_*), \sigma^2),$$

where the mean $\mu(z_*)$ and variance $\sigma^2(z_*)$ are given respectively by:

$$\begin{aligned} \mu(z_*) &= k(z_*, Z)k(z_*, Z)^T K(Z, Z)^{-1} f(Z), \\ \sigma^2(z_*) &= k(z_*, z_*) - k(z_*, Z)^T K(Z, Z)^{-1} k(z_*, Z). \end{aligned}$$

Here, Z represents the matrix of training latent variables, $K(Z, Z)$ is the covariance matrix of the training points, and $k(z_*, Z)$ is the covariance between the test point and the training points. The mean $\mu(z_*)$ represents the GP’s prediction for the latent variable at z_* , while the variance $\sigma^2(z_*)$ quantifies the uncertainty of the prediction. Anomalies can be detected in two ways:

- High uncertainty: if $\sigma^2(z_*)$ is large, it indicates that the test point lies far from the training data in the latent space, indicating an outlier or anomaly.
- Deviating mean: if the predicted latent variable $\mu(z_*)$ deviates significantly from the typical values observed during training, it could also signal an anomaly. This occurs when the test point is far from the expected behaviour learned from the training data.

To quantify the likelihood of a point being an anomaly, an anomaly score can be defined as:

$$\text{Anomaly score}(z_*) = \|z_* - \mu(z_*)\|^2 + \sigma^2(z_*).$$

HITL-RL for Semantic error detection and correction

Semantic errors arising from changes in human subjective values cannot be addressed by the GP method, as the data distribution in the latent space remains unchanged. To manage this

type of error, the SemCom framework must incorporate direct user feedback. By collecting feedback on user satisfaction with the current SemCom service, the system can proactively adjust and update its models. This includes managing and updating the KB, tuning NN model hyperparameters, and addressing channel noise during JSCC training.

Therefore, we propose to use HITL-RL in the SemCom to: (1) keep the users of SemCom service actively and continuously involved during the learning and updating process; (2) enable the RL agent to make certain decisions of the SemCom model re-training/tuning with these human's value.

In HITL-RL, the human interactions are integrated into the standard RL process to guide the agent's exploration and policy updates. In a typical RL setting, an agent interacts with an environment, modelled as a Markov Decision Process (MDP) defined by the tuple $\langle S, A, P, R, \gamma \rangle$, where S is the state space, A is the action space, $P(s'|s, a)$ is the state transition probability, $R(s, a)$ is the reward function and $\gamma \in [0, 1]$ is the discount factor. The goal of the agent is to learn a policy $\pi(a|s)$, which maximizes the expected cumulative reward [LTW+22]:

$$J(\pi) = E_{\pi} \left[\sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \gamma^t R(s_t, a_t) \right]$$

In HITL-RL, human feedback modifies the reward signal or policy to improve learning. Let $f_h(s_t, a_t)$ represent the human feedback function. The modified reward function $\tilde{R}(s_t, a_t)$ becomes a combination of environment rewards and human feedback:

$$\tilde{R}(s_t, a_t) = R(s_t, a_t) + \alpha f_h(s_t, a_t),$$

where α is a weighting factor determining the influence of human feedback. The overall workflow of HITL-RL for SemCom can be described in the following steps:

- The agent observes the state s_t and selects an action a_t^{agent} according to its policy $\pi_{\theta}(a|s)$ to change the SemCom models training hyperparameters and re-train/fine-tune the SemCom model, wherein θ represents the parameters of the policy function π .
- The agent updates its action to \tilde{a}_t based on human intervention (if applicable).
- The reward $\tilde{R}(s_t, a_t)$ is computed using both environmental (SemCom setting) rewards and human feedback.
- The policy π_{θ} is updated using the modified reward and the standard policy gradient method.

Figure 4-3: SemCom model adjust via HITL-RL

Results

Distribution deviation identification with Gaussian processes

GP for semantic error detection and correction

As discussed in the previous section, GP can be employed for latent space monitoring to detect semantic errors caused by input feature changes, channel noise and variations, as well as adversarial attacks targeting the semantic encoder/decoder. To validate the effectiveness of GP, we conducted three separate experiments.

Each GP was trained on the latent space using a radial basis function (RBF) kernel. For each test sample's latent representation, the GP computes the predictive mean and variance, from which anomaly scores are derived.

Figure 4-4: Latent vector monitoring with GP for three types of error sources.

GP for input feature change detection

We use the MNIST dataset for the VAE-based SemCom model training and GP training (on the latent variables). However, we feed the CIFAR-10 dataset jointly with MNIST data into the trained model to mimic the change of input features during the deployment stage of the VAE model. In this process, we use the GP model to identify the abnormal distribution caused by the CIFAR-10 dataset in the latent space. In this process, the threshold of anomaly scores is set to 0.02. The anomaly detection results are shown in Figure 4-5.

It can be seen from the confusion matrix (Figure 4-5c) that the GP is able to identify most of the anomalous inputs from the normal inputs.

Figure 4-5: GP-based anomaly detection for input feature change: (a) ROC curve; (b) t-SNE of latent space; (c) confusion matrix; (d) VAE reconstruction comparison (correct/incorrect input).

GP for channel change detection

We use the AWGN in JSCC to train the VAE model initially. However, we assume in its deployment stage, the channel is changed from the AWGN to a Rayleigh fading channel. Then the GP is used to detect the abnormal points in the latent space caused by the channel change. The detection results are illustrated in Figure 4-5. It can be seen that the change of channel features do have an impact on the reconstruction results of images Figure 4-5d, even if the distribution

of normal/abnormal points has no significant deviation in the latent space, while the GP is able to detect the anomalous in the latent space.

GP for adversarial attack detection

In this case, we still use the MNIST dataset to train the VAE model and GP is trained using the latent space distribution of VAE. However, we assume the adversarial attack is applied to the VAE (the semantic encoder more specifically) in the deployment stage using the FGSM algorithm. The trained GP model is leveraged to identify the adversarial anomalous. From the results shown in Figure 4-7, it can be seen that delicate designed adversarial noise has a huge impact on the VAE's image reconstruction, and a noise perturbed number ``7" almost cannot be reconstructed by the VAE (Figure 4-7d). However, GP has a good performance in detecting the latent variables affected by the adversarial noise (Figure 4-7c). It should be noted that in this case, the threshold of anomaly scores should be carefully selected, which is been set to 0.001 in this experiment.

Figure 4-6: GP anomaly detection in JSCC with channel change: (a) ROC curve; (b) t-SNE of latent space; (c) confusion matrix; (d) VAE reconstruction comparison (AWGN vs. Rayleigh fading).

Figure 4-7: GP anomaly detection for the semantic encoder adversarial attacks: (a) ROC curve; (b) t-SNE of latent space; (c) confusion matrix; (d) VAE reconstruction comparison (normal vs. adversarial noise perturbed input).

HITL-RL for semantic error detection and correction

To verify the effectiveness of HITL-RL for semantic error detection and correction. We design a SemCom system that incorporates HITL-RL to optimize a VAE model in a multi-user JSCC broadcasting scenario. Specifically, we aim to improve the VAE's ability to reconstruct images under varying channel conditions and input characteristics by leveraging user feedback to dynamically adjust the training process.

In our experimental design, we consider a SemCom system where a transmitter communicates with five UE devices over Gaussian noise channels with different noise levels. We utilize the MNIST dataset for image data. During the initial training phase, the VAE model is trained exclusively on images of odd digits (labels 1, 3, 5, 7, 9) from the MNIST dataset, and we simulate an

ideal channel with a noise standard deviation of zero. This setup represents a scenario where the model has not been exposed to certain input $\sigma = 0$ features (even digits) or channel imperfections.

In the deployment phase, both odd and even digits are transmitted. Each UE experiences a different channel noise level, with standard deviations $\sigma_i \in \{0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5\}$ for $i = 1, 2, \dots, 5$, respectively. Upon receiving the transmitted data, each UE reconstructs the image using the VAE decoder and provides feedback in the form of the mean squared error (MSE) between the original and reconstructed images. We use the score of MSE to mimic/indicate the human feedback after human's observation.

The HITL-RL training curve is illustrated in Figure 4-8. It can be observed that by iteratively updating the VAE model and the DQN agent through episodes consisting of time steps, the SemCom system learns to adapt to varying channel conditions and input data characteristics.

Figure 4-8: HITL-RL training reward over episodes for the multi-user JSCC broadening SemCom system

Conclusions

This work addresses the critical issue of semantic errors in goal-oriented SemCom systems by developing a comprehensive error detection and correction framework. We defined semantic errors, detection, and correction, and identified the root causes of these errors within practical communication scenarios. To effectively address semantic errors, we proposed a GP-based method for monitoring latent space deviations, as well as a HITL-RL approach to optimize semantic model parameters based on user feedback. Our experimental results demonstrated the robustness and adaptability of the proposed methods in handling semantic errors under various challenging conditions, including adversarial attacks, input feature changes, physical channel variations, and evolving user preferences. Future work may explore further optimisations and extensions of the framework to enhance its generalization and application in more diverse communication environments.

4.2 Pragmatic goal-oriented communication

Context and motivation

Future 6G networks must integrate AI-driven communication that conveys meaningful, goal-oriented data rather than raw information. Current approaches focus on symbol-level accuracy,

disregarding the conveyed meaning. Semantic and goal-oriented communications aim to optimize information exchange for task execution, requiring a shared language among autonomous agents. However, language mismatches introduce semantic noise, leading to interpretation errors. This work presented in this section, and detailed in [HSC24], addresses such mismatches by modelling their effects and proposing a corrective algorithm based on optimal transport theory. The contribution of this work is three-fold: (1) We extend a previous work [SS23] to language mismatch between agents in a Markov Decision Process (MDP) context, thus studying language mismatch in a pragmatic communications problem (2) we propose a novel mathematical model for errors stemming from language mismatch at both semantic and effectiveness levels and, (3) we propose an equalization algorithm that leverages optimal transport theory to counteract language mismatches and show its efficacy on a practical example.

System model and problem statement

We consider the system model shown in Figure 4-9. A transmitter observes the states of a stochastic environment, and encodes the underlying information for a distant receiver, which rules it to an action to complete a task. Communication takes place over an error-prone wireless channel, in several rounds, until the task is completed or it fails. To achieve the task, both encoder and decoder employ distinct languages (different logic), here artificially modelled with NN, which we respectively refer to as language generator and language interpreter.

Figure 4-9 System model

A language generator maps an observation of the world into a latent vector, and is defined as $\lambda : O \rightarrow X$, where O is the observation space and X is the semantic space. The semantic representation captures the intrinsic structure of the data, which is useful for solving downstream tasks. It is worth noting that the language generator can implement either a one-to-one mapping or a many-to-one or one-to-many mapping. A language interpreter transforms a semantic representation into a task specific action in each communication round, and is defined as $\gamma : X \rightarrow A$, where A denotes the action space. More specifically, a language interpreter defines a strategy for interpreting the semantic partition defined by the language generator to solve the downstream task.

An effective communication between the encoder and decoder requires a joint learning procedure, during which a shared language emerges to solve the downstream task. However, even with the same NN architecture and constraints, different training processes can yield different languages which nevertheless achieve similar performances on the task. When the language generator and interpreter are the result of different training procedures, communication may suffer from language mismatch or incompatibility that stimulates effectiveness errors. This is the focus of our work, to define a novel framework to counteract and limit the critical errors in interpretation to achieve effective communication.

Proposed methodology and solution

As the source and target language differ, an observation o may be mapped to symbol $x_s = \lambda_s(o)$ by the source language, and to symbol $x_t = \lambda_t(o)$ by the target language. Semantic mismatch may arise if x_s and x_t do not belong to the same small region of the target language partition. Hence, we introduce the following metric to quantify the semantic mismatch between source language λ and target language γ , which were defined above, as:

$$SM(l_s, l_t) = 1 - \sum_{o \in \mathcal{O}} \mu(o) \int_X 1_{[\lambda_t(o)]_t}(x) \mu_{\lambda_s}(x|o) dx,$$

where $\mu(o)$ denotes the probability of encountering a observation o .

Intuitively, SM characterizes the probability of semantic misinterpretation between the two languages, measuring how often the intended meaning is misinterpreted. However, errors at the semantic level do not necessarily translate to errors at effectiveness level.

The effectiveness mismatch is a metric centred around the actions and how they affect the performance on the task. This metric assesses the impact of misinterpretations on task performance:

$$EM(l_s, l_t) = 1 - \sum_{o \in \mathcal{O}} \mu(o) \frac{Q^+(o, \hat{a}(o))}{Q^+(o, a^*(o))},$$

where $Q(o, a)$ represents the action-value function from reinforcement learning theory, $a^*(o)$ is the optimal action that maximizes Q for a given observation o and $\hat{a}(o)$ is the interpreted action by the received when the source encoder λ_s , but decoder using the target decoder γ_t .

To address these mismatches, a **semantic equalization** process is introduced. This equalization is done to align the transmitter's semantic space with the receiver's semantic space. This equalization is through measurable transformations, which is a function that transforms values measured by a probability distribution into values measured by another probability distribution. We call a transformation $T : X \rightarrow X$ a semantic equalizer.

A transformation codebook is constructed to map source semantic representations to target representations, minimizing misinterpretations. The transformation codebook consists of a finite set of mappings. Each transformation in the codebook aims to map a source semantic region onto a corresponding target region, preserving task-relevant meaning while compensating for inherent differences between language generators.

Optimal transport theory is employed to identify the most effective transformation, ensuring minimal deviation from the intended message. The transformation is obtained by solving the following equation:

$$T^* = \arg \min_{T \in \mathcal{T}} f(T \ell_s, \ell_t),$$

where f represents either the semantic or effectiveness mismatch function.

A probabilistic selection policy $\pi(o, T)$ determines the best transformation to apply based on minimizing either semantic or effectiveness mismatch risk. The selection policy ensures that equalization is dynamically applied based on real-time communication conditions, optimizing either semantic understanding or goal performance.

Results

The proposed method is tested in a reinforcement learning scenario where an agent navigates a grid world to reach a goal. During training of the agents and languages, SNR is 10dB.

Independent training leads to different yet effective semantic partitions. First, we analyse how language structures vary based on training conditions and evaluate their effectiveness in noisy communication environments. Figure 4-10 shows the mapping of the learned languages. Both encoder-decoder pairs were trained to solve the same task in identical conditions only differing

in stochastic training aspects. We see that each language follows a logic that divides the semantic space in different ways with a successful task competition. The semantic and effectiveness mismatches are also illustrated.

Figure 4-10 Emergent Learning Diversity

Next, we evaluate language equalization. Given that task performance is given by how long does it take to reach the goal, a lower value is better in the performance evaluation below. We compare the equalization method proposed with a solution without any equalization, and with source/target grounded communication.

Figure 4-11 Language Equalization

From Figure 4-11, we see that our methods are effective on minimizing the language mismatch effects on the performance since the performance improves for all values of SNR when compared to the no equalization approach. However, the equalization methods perform worse than

the base languages. This can be explained by the resilience of the proposed methods to channel noise, indeed, as the developed methods reduce the effect of the wireless channel noise, this enforces the systematic errors of the language and causes an increase in the average episode length.

Conclusions

This contribution presents a framework to model and mitigate semantic-effectiveness errors in goal-oriented AI communications. By leveraging optimal transport theory, the proposed equalization algorithm effectively aligns disparate semantic representations, enhancing communication reliability. Our study highlights the importance of semantic robustness in AI-native communication frameworks, showing that mitigating semantic mismatches improves goal-oriented decision-making.

4.3 Soft Partitioning of Latent Space for Semantic Channel Equalization

Context and motivation

SemCom aims to transmit only task-relevant information, reducing bandwidth and energy consumption. However, a key challenge arises when independently trained encoders and decoders use different representations, leading to semantic mismatch and performance degradation. Traditional approaches require re-training, which is impractical in dynamic networks.

Semantic Channel Equalization (SCE) addresses this by partitioning the semantic space into distinct atoms and aligning the latent spaces of the mismatched encoders and decoders. Existing SCE methods rely on hard partitioning, where each semantic representation is strictly mapped to a single action based on a hard decision rule. This approach does not account for action ambiguities, where multiple actions can be optimal for a given observation. This work proposes a *soft partitioning* approach using action-value functions to refine the partitioning process, improving equalization performance and enabling robust communication in dynamic multi-agent settings.

The primary contribution of this section, based on [HSC24S], lies in introducing a novel methodology for partitioning the latent space, which captures richer semantic meaning and consequently enhances the performance of SCE.

System model and problem statement

We consider a distributed inference problem where an encoder transforms observations into semantic representations, which a decoder interprets to select actions. The communication occurs over a noisy channel, and we assume that the encoder and decoder languages result from separate training. SCE mitigates language mismatch by aligning the atoms of these partitions. However, conventional hard partitioning assumes a one-to-one mapping between actions and partitions, leading to suboptimal performance in tasks with action ambiguities.

The system consists of:

- An encoder $\lambda : O \rightarrow X$ that maps observations into a semantic representation.
- A decoder $\gamma : X \rightarrow A$ that selects an action based on the received semantic representation.
- A noisy channel with probability distribution $p(y|x)$.

Through a joint learning process, agents estimate an action-value function $Q(s, a)$ which guides decision-making via a greedy policy.

A key challenge arises when the encoder and decoder are trained separately, leading to semantic mismatch, where the transmitted representation $x_s = \lambda_s(o)$ is not interpreted correctly by the target decoder. This mismatch occurs due to differences in partitioning the semantic

space X . Semantic Channel Equalization (SCE) aims to compensate for this mismatch by aligning source and target semantic partitions. The equalization process involves selecting transformations T from a codebook to align mismatched semantic partitions.

Figure 4-12 System model and proposed soft-partition

The quantity $\rho_{P_i^s \rightarrow P_j^t}(T)$ measures the overlap between source and target atoms after a transformation T . We define two equalization policies:

Semantic Equalization Policy π_{sem} : Aims to perfectly align source and target atoms according to their semantic meaning:

$$\pi_{sem} = \arg \max_{T \in \mathcal{T}} \sum_{i=1}^{J_s} \mu_{\lambda_s}(P_i^s | o) \sum_{j \in \kappa(i)} \rho_{P_i^s \rightarrow P_j^t}(T).$$

Effectiveness Equalization Policy π_{eff} : Optimizes task performance by considering action-value functions:

$$\pi_{eff} = \arg \max_{T \in \mathcal{T}} \sum_{i=1}^{J_s} \mu_{\lambda_s}(P_i^s | o) \sum_{j=1}^{J_t} \rho_{P_i^s \rightarrow P_j^t}(T) Q_t(o, a_j).$$

Traditional hard partitioning assigns each semantic symbol strictly to one action, but this approach fails in scenarios with action ambiguities (multiple valid actions for the same observation). We propose a soft partitioning approach, where clustering is applied in the action-value space instead of using hard decision boundaries. This allows for a more flexible and structured semantic space, improving equalization performance and reducing the loss of critical task-related information.

Proposed methodology and solution

Traditional hard partitioning assigns semantic representations based on the highest-valued action, ignoring action ambiguities. This results in irregular partitions that degrade equalization. Hard partitioning is defined as:

$$P_i = \{x \in X | x = \lambda(o), \gamma(x) = \arg \max_{a \in A} Q(o, a)\}.$$

However, when multiple actions yield similar values, this approach loses information. We propose soft partitioning using clustering in the action-value space. The general idea is to partition the action-value space into clusters and translate this into the semantic space. The clustering divides the action-value space into n_c clusters. Then, we can define a partition of the semantic space as:

$$P = \{P_0, P_1, \dots, P_{n_c-1}\},$$

where each atom in the is constructed as:

$$P_i = \{\lambda(o) \mid o \in O, C(Q(o, \cdot)) = i\}.$$

The choice of the clustering algorithm is not simple and it is most likely problem dependent. In our work we choose to use the well-known k-means algorithm [HW79]. This algorithm requires to define the number of atoms n_c beforehand so we test multiple atom numbers in our experiments. While we are aware of the limitations of the algorithm with respect to convergence, the need to define the number of clusters beforehand and also the clustering criteria, we chose k-means both for its simplicity and popularity. Finding the optimal clustering criteria is beyond the scope of this contribution, our objective is rather to show the influence of different latent space partition on SCE.

Results

Experiments were conducted in a reinforcement learning-based grid world to evaluate different semantic space partitioning approaches. The action-space is discrete and has 4 actions, move up, down, right or left. During training of the agents and languages, SNR is 5dB.

We first explore the possible semantic space partitions for the learned languages. In Figure 4-13 we show the resulting partitions on the semantic space when using k-means on the action-value space for multiple choices of number of atoms n_c . The actions (hard partitioning) are visualized as different shapes for each partition. The colour of the points corresponds to a given atom and the actions associated with each atom are shown next to it in the colour legend.

Figure 4-13 Semantic space partitioning

In general, we can observe that the resulting atoms are more regular in shape compared to the hard partitioning (which is indicated by the shape of the plotted points). Different partitions capture different semantic descriptions of the task. However, for four and six atoms, the semantic meaning for some individual actions is lost, as we will show next, this will be detrimental for the performance of the equalization.

Leveraging these partitions of the semantic space, we implement both equalization policies π_{sem} and π_{eff} introduced by the SCE framework as described. The results of the performance

evaluations comparing semantic channel equalization for both hard-partitioning and soft-partitioning with different number of clusters are shown below.

Figure 4-14 Performance results

From Figure 4-14, we observe that soft partitioning with $n_c = 8$ is the best, since it is the smallest number of atoms for which we observe the best performance, providing the best balance between capturing semantic information and complexity. Fewer clusters led to information loss, while excessive clustering increased complexity without further gains. Using fewer atoms resulted in lost semantic information, while excessive atoms added unnecessary complexity. Soft partitioning significantly improved task completion time compared to hard partitioning, as it better preserved task-relevant semantics.

Conclusions

This contribution highlights the impact of semantic space partitioning on SCE performance. We demonstrate that hard partitioning oversimplifies the latent space, reducing equalization effectiveness. By incorporating soft-value clustering, we achieve more structured partitions, enhancing communication robustness. These findings suggest potential applications in multi-task semantic equalization, paving the way for improved AI-driven communication systems.

4.4 Relative representation for latent space alignment

Employing deep learning to design SemCom protocols, also referred to as semantic languages, has been shown to largely outperform traditional communication systems. So far, most works in the SemCom literature share one key assumption: the communication language has been previously learned and is fixed during deployment. However, assuming that all agents participating in the communication have undergone a joint training procedure limits the application of SemCom. In scenarios such as autonomous vehicles or IoT networks, the agents and their objectives must continuously adapt to changing conditions. Regularly unifying the language is an energy consuming process that could outweigh the advantages of SemCom. Therefore, it is crucial to ensure that the semantic protocols in use enable effective task-solving under such dynamic scenarios.

The divergence in semantic languages is referred to as semantic mismatch and Semantic Channel Equalization algorithms have been proposed to equalize the semantic mismatch between a transmitter and a receiver. However, previous solutions required either the identification of the atoms in different RRs models or training a solution to define the atoms. In this section, we explore the concept of RRs [MMF+22] for correct the semantic mismatch, to establish a common communication channel between different semantic protocols in a zero-shot manner, without the need for retraining the models or labelled data.

RRs were introduced as a method to project the data embedding of different models into a unified representation space. Instead of relying on the latent coordinates of each model, the authors propose to use a RR whose components are the similarity score between the desired data embedding and a set of predefined points called anchors. This way, the semantic meaning extracted by different models could be unified if the similarity function is sensible to the way these models encode information.

4.4.1 Accuracy-compression trade-off in relative representation based semantic communications

Context and motivation

Semantic channel equalization aims to minimize semantic noise during communication. In this work, the semantic noise is modeled as a latent space mismatch. Therefore, the primary objective is to reconstruct the expected input for the receiver's encoding scheme. This reframes the decoding challenge as a latent alignment problem rather than a signal restoration problem — which is central to SemCom.

Previous works have demonstrated how to recover the original absolute representation, thereby eliminating the need for a relative decoder and enabling zero-shot semantic channel equalization. Specifically, [MMF+24] employs the pseudo-inverse of the anchor matrix, \mathbf{A}^\dagger , to recover the absolute representation. In contrast, [HFS+24] utilizes an optimisation algorithm to reconstruct the original absolute representation generalizing semantic channel equalization to any similarity function d .

In this work, the relative representation is framed within the general context of frame theory, leveraging the advantageous properties of the simple and stable Parseval reconstruction formula. The work considers signal expansion and compression, giving additional flexibility to the communication system.

System model and problem statement

Consider a communication system where the transmitter (TX) and receiver (RX) employ two distinct encoding schemes, denoted as $E_\theta: \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^d$ for the TX and $E_\psi: \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^p$ for the RX. Accordingly, each side has a decoder specifically trained to interpret its associated latent space, i.e., the collections of the expected input vectors, namely \mathcal{X}_θ for the TX and \mathcal{X}_ψ for the RX. We label these decoders as D_θ and D_ψ , respectively. Because these components have been independently optimized, the TX's encoder is not directly compatible with the RX's decoder, resulting in a latent space mismatch problem.

Proposed methodology and solution

In [FBC+25], we revised the RRs through the lens of frame theory, enabling a robust and simple zero-shot semantic channel equalization. First, a random selection of N samples is made from the dataset \mathcal{X} to define the *support set*,

$$S_N = \{s_1, \dots, s_N\} \subseteq \mathcal{X}.$$

Assume the embedding of each sample of the support set is computed by a generic embedding function to generate the sequence of independent vectors that span the associated latent space \mathcal{X}_θ , i.e., $\{f_n\}_{n=1}^N \subseteq \mathcal{X}_\theta$. So, it is possible to define the *analysis operator* \mathbf{F} and the analysis operation $\mathbf{F}\mathbf{x} = \{\langle \mathbf{x}, f_n \rangle\}_{n=1}^N$. The adjoint of \mathbf{F} is called the *synthesis operator*. Instead, the frame operator $\mathbf{S}: \mathcal{X}_\theta \rightarrow \mathcal{X}_\theta$ is defined as

$$\mathbf{S}\mathbf{x} = \sum_{n=1}^N \langle \mathbf{x}, f_n \rangle f_n.$$

This formulation is a specific instance of RRs, using the inner product as the similarity function d . Then, the use of Parseval Frames, enabled via a simple transformation of the original frame,

$$\tilde{\mathbf{F}} = \mathbf{S}^{(-1/2)} \mathbf{F},$$

guarantees a stable yet straightforward reconstruction formula at the receiver. In this case, the frame operator becomes the identity matrix, resulting in a well-conditioned matrix (condition number equal to 1) that simplifies the frame operation.

This preparation is performed by all the system devices using the shared set S_N and the local DNN model. When the latent spaces do not have the same dimension, i.e., when $d \neq p$, we choose S_N to have at least $N = \max(d, p)$, ensuring that both original latent spaces are fully spanned. Nevertheless, a larger N may be beneficial in practice. Specifically, introducing redundancy in the basis, i.e., $N > \max(d, p)$, helps to mitigate the impact of semantic noise and ensures a more robust semantic channel equalization.

The inherent alignment of RRs is unknown a priori. However, it assumes the existence of a mapping T that aligns the two spaces, i.e.,

$$\langle \mathbf{x}, \mathbf{f}_n \rangle \approx \langle T\mathbf{y}, T\mathbf{g}_n \rangle = \langle \mathbf{y}, \mathbf{g}_n \rangle.$$

This condition is satisfied by angle-preserving transformations. Intuitively, this methodology is intrinsically limited by the performance of such transformations.

Finally, the coefficients produced by the analysis operation of the TX embedding function (which may be unknown to the RX) are transmitted using the shared support set S_N . Consequently, the RX input is approximated following the Parseval Reconstruction Formula (PRF),

$$\sum_{n=1}^N \langle \mathbf{x}, \mathbf{f}_n \rangle \mathbf{g}_n \approx \hat{\mathbf{y}},$$

enabling seamless semantic understanding without any additional optimisation step.

Signal Compression. From a frame-theoretic perspective, removing a vector from a frame will leave either another frame or an incomplete set. Consequently, signal compression makes full reconstruction of the original space impossible. The frame operator \mathbf{S} becomes rank-deficient, so its inverse does not exist. Instead, the Moore–Penrose pseudoinverse is employed to compute $\mathbf{F} = \mathbf{S}^{(-1/2)} \mathbf{F}$. The new operator \mathbf{F} is a partial isometry, implying it remains well-conditioned in the subspace corresponding to its nonzero singular values. Moreover, the frame operator acts as an orthogonal projection, ensuring stability in that subspace and yielding an orthogonal approximation of the original vector.

Prototypical Anchors. Since orthogonality is ensured by the design of the analysis operator and we are focused on task-oriented applications (e.g., classification), the method naturally leverages the denser regions of the latent space. For these reasons, we consider Prototypical Anchors (PAs) an effective technique for defining S_N . A clustering algorithm is applied to the latent space of a chosen encoder, setting the number of clusters N equal to the desired number of vectors. Ideally, the clustered space should be divided according to the N most relevant semantic features of the data. Each cluster’s centroid is selected as the most representative point because it maximizes separation from other clusters according to the chosen clustering metric. However, selecting the cluster centroids directly is not feasible since they are grounded in the absolute space of the selected encoder and thus cannot be directly transferred to the latent spaces of other encoders. For this reason, we estimate the centroids by randomly selecting M samples from each cluster and taking the mean of their absolute representations as the centroid estimation. This approach allows each encoder to independently compute its anchor set (i.e., support set) by sharing the same data samples.

Use of a set of relative decoders at the RX. In [FBC+24], a simpler approach is presented. Here, instead of reconstructing the original signal in the absolute space of the RX, it is assumed to have more relative decoders trained for each support set, i.e., varying N , and enabling a possible dynamic compression of the transmitted message. This approach requires more resources

(allocating memory for different decoders and spending time in a training procedure) and is less flexible but, at the same time, do not face the instability problem given by the reconstruction formula.

Results

We compared the proposed methodology with two different baselines. The first involves using a redundant basis composed of a random selection of N samples to build the support set. In this case, the analysis operator is directly F , without additional steps, and the reconstruction of the vector employs the inverse of the frame operator, i.e., the reconstruction formula. The second baseline is an alignment via the Procrustes problem, which serves as a supervised upper bound since the solution is an orthogonal transformation aligning the two spaces. Note that, in this case, the absolute representation is always transmitted, and no redundancy or compression is introduced.

Figure 4-15 Accuracy vs. transmitted coefficients N for RF, PRF, and Procrustes solutions, demonstrating PRF's robustness under latent-space mismatch.

Figure 4-15 illustrates the performance of our frame-based approach, comparing the RF, PRF, and Procrustes solutions on CIFAR-10, Coarse CIFAR-100, CIFAR-100 and Tiny-ImageNet. We selected several pre-trained DNNs from the trimm library. At the RX side, we used a single decoder function, trained specifically to interpret the 'absolute' representations from one of those pre-trained models. Meanwhile, at the TX side, we transmit the coefficients formed by the other models through this same decoder. This setup enables us to test the robustness of our task-oriented communication framework under latent space mismatches. The “absolute” curve in each plot represents a fully E2E trained baseline. From the results, it can be observed that PRF is more stable and outperforms the classical RF. Furthermore, increasing the size of the vector sequence leads to a slight performance gain, likely because the redundant basis helps reduce semantic noise during transmission. Finally, the PRF curves converge toward the corresponding Procrustes solutions, indicating that this zero-shot framework closely approximates the performance of supervised methods.

Figure 4-16 Accuracy vs. transmitted coefficients N for PRF with and without prototypical anchors.

In Figure 4-16, instead, we used the PRF with and without the use of prototypical anchors. It shows that for a small number of used coefficients, the PAs significantly improve performance in terms of accuracy.

Conclusions

In [FBC+25], a robust framework for zero-shot semantic channel equalization is presented by framing RRs within the context of frame theory. The proposed methodology effectively aligns latent spaces mitigating semantic channel noise during communication by leveraging the Parseval Reconstruction formula. Prototypical Anchors [HFS+24] are employed as a simple, task-oriented support set selection mechanism, demonstrating their capacity to characterize denser regions of the latent spaces. Instead, in [FBC+24], the integration of relative decoders into the communication system is studied, eliminating the need for a separate reconstruction phase.

Experimental results validate the proposed methodologies, demonstrating flexibility in extending and compressing the signal while mitigating semantic mismatches that can occur in multi-agent systems. Overall, this framework offers a promising solution for achieving reliable, AI-driven SemCom.

This result will be used in [6GGOALS-D42] to enable seamless semantic understanding in communication systems under timing constraints.

4.4.2 Semantic channel equalization via relative representation

Context and motivation

Traditional communication systems prioritize accurate data transmission but disregard its meaning, such like task-relevant features or decisions. With AI-driven SemCom, intelligent agents exchange meaningful representations rather than raw data. However, independently trained models develop unique semantic languages, leading to mismatches that hinder effective communication.

Existing solutions require retraining or extensive data exchange, making them impractical for dynamic environments like autonomous systems or IoT networks. The work in this section [HFS+24] introduces RRs, which allow different models to communicate by projecting their semantic representations into a shared space. By leveraging anchor-based projections, this method enables efficient and adaptable semantic equalization without retraining, ensuring interoperability between heterogeneous models.

The main contributions are:

- We propose a semantic equalization framework based on RRs that does not need any retraining and requires sharing a small amount of data between transmitter and receiver.
- We introduce a novel anchor selection algorithm called prototypical anchors, which improves the performance of semantic equalization compared to classical approaches such as random selection

System model and problem statement

Figure 4-17 Illustration of the considered problem

In a multi-user SemCom scenario, a transmitter extracts features and sends them to a receiver for task completion. Traditional methods transmit raw data, whereas SemCom transmit mean-

ing. However, mismatches arise when agents have different learned representations. The proposed solution uses RRs to align semantic spaces and ensure communication effectiveness. Formally, we define the communication process as:

- The transmitter E_θ maps an observation $x \in X$ into a semantic representation $z_\theta = E_\theta(x)$.
- The receiver D_γ should ideally recover the task-relevant information $y_\gamma = D_\gamma(z_\gamma)$, but due to model differences $z_\theta \neq z_\gamma$.
- A transformation function $T_{\theta \rightarrow \gamma}$ ensures that the received representation z_γ is close enough to z_θ for the task to be completed effectively.

This procedure is illustrated in Figure 4-17.

Semantic channel equalization (SCE) ensures that semantic representations align despite model differences. A transformation function maps source representations into a target space, optimizing for either perfect alignment or effective task completion. Previous approaches rely on codebooks or self-supervised methods, but these require extensive data exchange. Instead, RRs unify different semantic spaces through anchor-based projections, creating a shared latent space.

Relative representations project absolute embeddings into a space defined by similarity to selected anchors. These anchors serve as reference points, ensuring consistency across models. Given a set of anchors $A = \{a^{(1)}, a^{(2)}, \dots, a^{(|A|)}\} \subset X$, the RR is computed as:

$$R_\theta(z_\theta) = r_\theta = \left[\psi(z_\theta, a_\theta^{(1)}), \psi(z_\theta, a_\theta^{(2)}), \dots, \psi(z_\theta, a_\theta^{(|A|)}) \right],$$

where ψ is a similarity function. This ensures that representations from different models are aligned in the relative space. RRs provide two main advantageous properties:

For two encoders E_θ and E_γ , the RRs of the same data samples x (using the same similarity function and set of anchors) are similar $r_\theta \approx r_\gamma, \forall x \in X$.

The RRs also carry the task-relevant information: a decoder D_{rel} trained on the RR of an encoder E_θ can successfully learn the given task with similar performance as a decoder D_θ trained using the absolute representations of E_θ .

Proposed methodology and solution

Figure 4-18 Proposed solution leveraging relative representations

We aim to design a semantic equalizer using relative representations to enable communication between independently trained agents without retraining. If the relative projection was an invertible process, it would be possible for a decoder D_γ to recover a semantic representation from

the RR r_θ transmitted by a non-matching encoder E_θ . The communication process through the common relative channel follows as:

$$\mathbf{x} \xrightarrow{E_\theta} \mathbf{z}_\theta \xrightarrow{R_\theta} \mathbf{r}_\theta \approx \mathbf{r}_\gamma \xrightarrow{R_\gamma^{-1}} \hat{\mathbf{z}}_\gamma \xrightarrow{D_\gamma} \hat{\mathbf{y}}$$

where R_θ and R_γ^{-1} are the transmitter relative projection and receiver relative projection inverse functions respectively. This is illustrated in Figure 4-18.

As such, it a method for relative projection inversion is necessary. For effective task solving, the exact inverse is not necessary, and the pseudo-inverse can be used. This pseudo-inverse can be obtained by solving the following optimisation problem:

$$z_\gamma^* = \arg \min_{z_\gamma \in Z_\gamma} |R_\gamma(z_\gamma) - r_\theta|^2$$

which we solve by using an algorithm based on gradient descent. For more details, refer to [HFS+24].

Another important point to touch is the selection of the RR anchor points. A clustering-based approach selects representative anchors that best capture key data features, improving alignment and reducing redundancy compared to random selection. Given clusters C_1, C_2, \dots, C_N and M samples, anchor prototypes are computed as:

$$a_\theta^{(i)} = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{s \in C_i} E_\theta(s)$$

A novel clustering-based approach refines the selection of anchors. This process is done via unsupervised clustering on the encoder space and it extracts representative samples as prototypical anchors. This clustering ensures that each cluster corresponds to meaningful features in the data.

Results

We tested our performance on an image classification task on the tiny-imagenet dataset¹, which is comprised of 100k 64x64 coloured images of 200 balanced classes. We selected a set of feature extractor models pre-trained on the Imagenet classification challenge to serve as the encoders of our scenario. For each of the feature extractors, we train a classifier network on top that we use as the decoder. This way, we obtain a set of different encoders with the corresponding decoders.

For the prototypical anchors we use K-Means as the clustering algorithm. For the similarity metric ψ , we explore the cosine similarity and the normalized Euclidean distance. We will compare our results with the pseudo-inverse solution where the cosine similarity-based RR is leveraged to obtain a closed-form solution.

We compare the performance of the proposed SCE algorithm (two leftmost columns) and the closed-form inverse (rightmost column) in Figure 4-19. Results are compared with a random anchor selection and the proposed prototypical anchors.

The results show that semantic equalization improves communication between differently trained models. It is also possible to see that the optimisation-based inverse mapping outperforms closed-form solutions. Also, prototypical anchors enhance accuracy compared to random selection.

In particular, it is interesting to see that the target decoder E_γ sometimes performs better when paired with a powerful equalized encoder E_θ rather than the matched encoder. This can be explained by the fact that a more descriptive encoder is capable of transmitting more information

¹ "Hugging face's tiny-imagenet repository." <https://huggingface.co/datasets/zh-plus/tiny-imagenet>. Accessed: 07/08/2024.

and that our method is effective in translating this information into the decoder space. The closed form inverse-based equalization has similar performance to our method but loses performance in the high anchor number regime, this can be explained by the instability of the matrix inverse when it's size increases.

Conclusions

In this contribution, we introduced a SCE algorithm based on relative representations, enabling a receiver to decode messages from an independently trained transmitter by exchanging only a small set of data points known as anchors. The algorithm supports compression, with data size depending on the number of anchors; including more anchors improves performance but reduces the compression ratio. We present a novel anchor selection strategy called prototypical anchors, which partitions the semantic space of an encoder to capture essential data features. Our results show that using prototypical anchors significantly enhances semantic equalization

performance compared to random selection. We also differentiate between semantic interpretation errors and performance loss, demonstrating that the latter is not solely determined by the former. Importantly, limitations in the encoding capabilities of a target model can be mitigated by employing a more powerful encoder at the transmitter.

4.5 Latent Space Alignment for AI-Native MIMO Semantic Communications

Context and motivation

In SemCom, two primary sources of noise are encountered ([GKB25], [LCG22]): *channel noise*, which distorts received symbols at the physical layer, and *semantic noise*, which arises from divergent methods of logic, interpretation, or knowledge among different devices.

Conventional handling of channel noise often separates the source and channel coding, achieving optimality in the asymptotic regime of infinite block length and unbounded complexity. Although suitable for traditional communication networks, this approach has proven suboptimal in practical finite block-length scenarios, especially for emerging applications. As a remedy, JSCC has been developed to map source signals directly into channel symbols, and deep learning has enabled end-to-end solutions that compress semantic information while also mitigating channel impairments ([BBG19], [YBK22], [WSB+24]).

However, most existing frameworks assume identical latent representations at transmitter and receiver, neglecting the issue of latent space misalignment, i.e., semantic noise stemming from heterogeneous encoding schemes. While several studies propose transformations between semantic spaces, the use of MIMO wireless channels for integrated semantic channel equalization has not yet been explored. Thus, an optimisation framework for AI-native, MIMO, semantic, and wireless communications is proposed in this section, and detailed in [PFC+25], addressing the impact of semantic noise modelled as latent space mismatch.

System model and problem statement

Our approach leverages MIMO channels to jointly address semantic alignment and wireless impairments within a unified framework. To enhance MIMO efficiency, semantic latent spaces are represented using complex-valued vectors to match the structure of MIMO signals. Here, without loss of generality, it is assumed that the transmitter's semantic vector has an even dimensionality d . The transmitter pairs the first half of the vector with the second half, creating complex symbols represented by the vector $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{C}^{d/2}$. A semantic MIMO precoder, represented by the transformation $f: \mathbb{C}^{d/2} \rightarrow \mathbb{C}^{KN_t}$ maps \mathbf{x} into transmitted signals. This transformation can compress the latent space, with the compression factor defined as

$$\zeta = \frac{KN_t}{d/2}.$$

Signals propagate through a wireless MIMO channel modelled as a flat Rayleigh fading scenario, characterized by a channel matrix \mathbf{H} that remains constant for K transmissions. At the receiver, a semantic MIMO decoder, $g: \mathbb{C}^{KN_t} \rightarrow \mathbb{C}^{m/2}$, maps the received signals to a complex latent vector:

$$\hat{\mathbf{y}} = g(\mathbf{H} f(\mathbf{x}) + \mathbf{v}),$$

where \mathbf{H} is the block-diagonal channel matrix and \mathbf{v} represents receiver noise modelled as complex Gaussian noise.

The objective is to optimize the transformations f and g so that the TX and RX latent spaces are closely aligned, thereby minimizing semantic noise. This alignment is achieved by reducing the semantic distance between the RX latent vectors and their received counterparts, guided by known data samples (semantic pilots).

Figure 4-20 System model: The semantic precoder f of TX encodes a compressed version of the latent space into a transmitter vector of dimension N_t . The encoded message is transmitted through the MIMO channel H . At the receiver side, the received vector is first decoded by the semantic decoder g and then is decompressed to match the real space of the latent space at RX.

Proposed methodology and solution

Two methods are described to jointly optimize semantic precoding and decoding, ensuring alignment between the semantic feature spaces at the TX and RX. Both methods assume knowledge of the MIMO channel. One employs linear transformations for semantic precoding and decoding, while the other uses non-linear transformations modelled by NNs.

Linear Semantic Precoding and Decoding. The precoding and decoding functions are modelled as linear transformations, represented by the matrix F and G , respectively. This formulation provides a simplified yet effective approach for modelling semantic encoding and decoding functions, allowing for tractable optimisation. Here, without loss of generality, pre-whitening is applied to standardize the covariance of the transmitted symbols to the identity matrix. Hence, the optimisation criteria aim to minimize

$$\min_{G, F} E \| \mathbf{y} - (G H F \mathbf{x} + G \mathbf{v}) \|_2^2$$

$$\text{subject to } \text{tr}(\mathbf{F} \mathbf{F}^H) \leq P_T,$$

where \mathbf{y} is the complex version of the RX latent vectors associated with training data without considering channel impairments, and $P_T > 0$ is the maximum TX power budget. The optimisation problem is reformulated to be amenable to a scaled ADMM solution, which efficiently handles the constraints and solves the bi-convex program.

Neural Semantic Precoding and Decoding. Here, the TX and RX transformations are modelled using nonlinear parametric functions, i.e., complex neural networks. These functions are trained to minimize

$$\min_{\theta, \psi} E \| \mathbf{y} - g_{\psi}(\mathbf{H} f_{\theta}(\mathbf{x}) + \mathbf{v}) \|_2^2 + \beta \| \theta \|_0 + \gamma \| \psi \|_0,$$

where \mathbf{y} denotes the target RX latent vectors. The terms $\| \theta \|_0$ and $\| \psi \|_0$ encourage sparsity in the model parameters, thereby reducing both storage and computational overhead.

The transmit power constraint is integrated directly into the neural network by applying L2 normalization to the semantic encoder's output. During training, noise samples \mathbf{v} are injected at the RX input to enhance robustness. The resulting problem is solved using a Proximal Gradient

Descent method and enforce sparsity in θ and ψ by applying a hard-thresholding step after each epoch.

Computational Complexity. The computational cost is quantified in terms of floating-point operations (FLOPs). For the linear model, the cost arises from two complex matrix multiplications (precoder and decoder). For the neural model, FLOPs include all the matrix multiplications and complex activations across its layers.

Results

In this section, the performance of the proposed semantic channel equalization methods is evaluated through numerical experiments, solving the CIFAR-10 classification task. Two pre-trained models from the Python library trimm are employed, with latent space dimensions of $d=384$ at the TX and $m=768$ at the RX. For simplicity, square MIMO Rayleigh fading channels are considered, where the number of transmitting and receiving antennas is set to be equal. The neural semantic precoder and decoder are implemented using a multilayer perceptron architecture.

We compare our methodology with baselines that directly transmit the TX latent vectors \mathbf{x} while performing semantic alignment and MIMO channel equalization separately. Specifically, we adopt an SVD-based MIMO channel equalization. Once the TX latent vectors \mathbf{x} are received, semantic alignment is performed to map them into the RX latent space using a linear transformation obtained by solving the associated least-squares problem.

To assess the performance of the baselines for different amounts of transmitted information, we consider two alternative strategies:

1. The "First-K baseline" (FK), which transmits the first KN_T features of \mathbf{x} ;
2. the Top-K baseline (Top-K), which selects and transmits the largest KN_T features of \mathbf{x} in terms of l_1 -norm.

In the latter case, to ensure accurate signal reconstruction at the receiver, the transmitted signal is structured such that half of the transmission space is allocated to the indices corresponding to the transmitted features. In contrast, the remaining half is dedicated to the features themselves. This allocation effectively doubles the communication burden. It is assumed that the indices are perfectly reconstructed at the receiver.

Figure 4-21 Accuracy versus ζ , with SNR=20dB and $\beta = \gamma = 0$.

Comparisons. The performance is illustrated in Figure 4-21 which shows the average accuracy of the classification task as a function of the compression factor ζ for different strategies.

Specifically, we compare:

- i. the proposed neural semantic precoding/decoding strategy,
- ii. the linear semantic precoding/decoding method,
- iii. the FK baseline, and
- iv. the Top-K baseline.

For the proposed neural and linear methods, we also examine their optimisation without wireless channel knowledge, referred to as “channel-unaware.” The results are obtained considering an SNR equal to 20dB and setting $\beta = \gamma = 0$. We explore different compression factors ζ by setting the channel usage equal to 1 and varying the number of antennas.

It is observed that the proposed semantic channel equalization strategies outperform the baselines, showing excellent performance even at significant compression levels. As expected, the channel-unaware methods perform poorly, further reinforcing the importance of incorporating physical channel information for effective semantic channel equalization in wireless communications.

Figure 4-22 Accuracy versus SNR, with an 8x8 MIMO channel, and $\zeta \approx 3\%$.

In Figure 4-22, the behaviour of the average accuracy versus the SNR is illustrated, comparing the proposed strategies with the baselines. In this scenario, an 8x8 MIMO channel is used with a single channel usage, yielding a compression factor of about 3%. The accuracy increases at higher SNR, and the neural model consistently outperforms its linear counterpart. However, the neural model requires significantly more computational resources, which is why the sparsification technique described previously is employed to address this complexity.

Finally, the results in Figure 4-23 illustrate the behaviour of the average accuracy versus the number of FLOPs, comparing the linear and neural approaches for different compression factors while fixing the SNR at 20 dB. The sparsified neural model maintains the same accuracy as the original model while requiring only approximately 10% of the original FLOPs. However, performance degrades significantly as the number of FLOPs approaches that of the linear model. This observation justifies the use of the linear approach under strict computational constraints, whereas the neural model becomes preferable when these constraints are more relaxed and performance must be prioritized.

Figure 4-23 Accuracy versus FLOPs.

Conclusions

In this section, a novel framework for latent space alignment in MIMO SemCom has been introduced, addressing the challenges posed by both semantic mismatch and channel distortions. Our approach integrates semantic compression with the alignment of semantic spaces through joint optimisation of MIMO semantic precoding and decoding, ensuring robust and efficient transmission. To solve this problem, we propose and evaluate two distinct methodologies. The first is a linear optimisation approach, formulated as a biconvex optimisation problem and solved using ADMM. The second is a NN-based solution that learns an optimized mapping between semantic representations and the transmitted signals. Numerical results demonstrate that the proposed approaches outperform the baselines available from the literature. Furthermore, the proposed neural model consistently outperforms the linear one across various channel conditions and noise levels, achieving superior alignment and robustness. However, this performance gain comes at the cost of increased computational complexity. To mitigate this issue, we applied sparsification to the NN model using Proximal Gradient Descent with Hard Thresholding, significantly reducing the FLOPs while preserving competitive accuracy. However, performance degrades significantly, as the number of FLOPs approaches that of the linear model. This finding highlights the suitability of the linear approach in scenarios with stringent computational limitations. At the same time, the neural model emerges as the better choice when computational resources allow for greater flexibility, and performance is the primary concern.

5 Goal/beliefs mismatch

In goal-oriented SemCom, successful information exchange relies not only on the accurate transmission of symbols but also on a shared understanding of goals, beliefs, and context between communicating entities. A fundamental challenge arises when the transmitter and receiver operate under different assumptions, leading to a mismatch in their respective goals, background knowledge, or reasoning processes. This discrepancy can severely impact communication efficiency, causing misunderstandings, misinterpretations, or suboptimal decision-making.

This section investigates the theoretical and practical aspects of goal/beliefs mismatches, including as well semantic alignment, in SemCom networks. We explore methods to bridge these gaps by leveraging advanced techniques such as pragmatic goal-oriented communication, optimal transport, and RDP theory. By integrating these approaches, we aim to develop adaptive frameworks that align mismatched knowledge representations, ensuring more robust and context-aware SemCom.

We first discuss how optimal transport theory can be used to address mismatches in common background knowledge by drawing insights from domain adaptation techniques. Then, we explore the intersection of optimal transport, RDP theory, and their potential to optimize communication strategies in scenarios where perfect alignment of knowledge is unattainable.

The results presented in this section contribute to advancing the resilience and adaptability of 6G goal-oriented AI-enabled SemCom networks, particularly in heterogeneous and dynamic environments where knowledge alignment cannot be assumed.

5.1 Belief Mismatch and Semantic Alignment using Optimal Transport

In goal-oriented SemCom, effective information exchange goes beyond mere data accuracy—it necessitates a mutual understanding of context, objectives, and intended meaning between the transmitter and receiver. However, when their internal knowledge representations and reasoning models are misaligned, belief mismatches arise, distorting interpretation and degrading communication effectiveness [PC19]. Traditional communication models prioritize signal fidelity, but they fail to address semantic discrepancies in meaning reconstruction [V08].

To address this challenge, we propose Optimal Transport (OT) as a structured framework for semantic alignment. Unlike conventional methods that focus on minimizing transmission errors at the symbol or data level, OT directly maps conceptual representations, ensuring that the receiver reconstructs information in alignment with the sender's intended meaning, even amid knowledge asymmetries [CFT+17, CFH+17]. This makes OT an effective tool for resolving semantic inconsistencies in dynamic, knowledge-driven communication environments.

In the context of semantic alignment, OT extends beyond traditional domain adaptation, which typically aligns structured input spaces such as different datasets or feature distributions, by addressing semantic adaptation. Here, the target distribution represents semantic knowledge rather than purely statistical distributions, and may be only partially observable or inferred through indirect observations [RCF+19]. This distinction presents additional challenges in ensuring that transported knowledge aligns with the underlying semantics of communication, rather than merely mapping low-level feature distributions.

From an information-theoretic perspective, OT provides an elegant framework for optimizing the transport of knowledge representations, offering a principled way to quantify and mitigate semantic misalignment [PC19]. Unlike conventional models that focus solely on minimizing distortion at the signal level, OT-based methods enable semantic fidelity-driven transmission, ensuring that knowledge is reconstructed in alignment with its intended meaning. Recent advancements in entropic OT techniques [C13, G19] offer computationally efficient solutions, allowing OT-based semantic alignment to be adaptable for real-time, dynamic communication environments.

By incorporating OT into goal-driven SemCom, we introduce a framework where belief mismatches are proactively corrected, improving interpretability, robustness, and adaptability. This ensures that transmitted messages are not only received but also understood in alignment with the sender's intent, even when prior knowledge and contextual assumptions differ [SCK+21].

System model and problem statement

We consider a scenario in which a source (e.g., a sensor or transmitter) aims to communicate information while ensuring that the received representation is close to the true semantic source distribution. However, the semantic source distribution is not fully known; rather, it can be partially observed, measured, or inferred through an indirect Rate-Distortion (RD) model.

Let:

- P_X denote the probability distribution of the source data.
- P_Y represent the unknown semantic source distribution.

- \hat{P}_Y be an estimate or partial observation of P_Y
- $T_\theta: X \rightarrow Y$ be a transport map parametrised by θ , aligning P_X to \hat{P}_Y .
- $c(x, y)$ define the cost of transporting $x \in X$ to $y \in Y$.

The general OT formulation seeks to minimize the expected transport cost:

$$W_c(P_X, \hat{P}_Y) = \inf_{\gamma \in \Pi(P_X, \hat{P}_Y)} E_{(X, Y) \sim \gamma} [c(X, Y)],$$

where $\Pi(P_X, \hat{P}_Y)$ is the set of all joint distributions with marginals P_X and \hat{P}_Y . In our case, the target distribution P_Y is not entirely known, making direct OT alignment infeasible. Instead, we introduce a regularization term based on the available measurements and domain adaptation techniques, leading to the following optimisation problem:

$$\min_{T_\theta} W_c(P_X, \hat{P}_Y) + \lambda D_{KL}(\hat{P}_Y || P_Y),$$

where $D_{KL}(\cdot || \cdot)$ denotes the Kullback-Leibler (KL) divergence, and λ is a regularization parameter controlling the trade-off between OT alignment and semantic fidelity. The inclusion of KL divergence here draws from information theory, where it serves as a measure of how much information is lost when approximating one distribution with another. This aligns with the semantic distortion minimization problem in indirect RD theory.

This formulation naturally extends to Entropic Optimal Transport (EOT) methods, where an entropy regularization term is added to ensure smoother transport solutions and relates to information bottleneck (IB) principles:

$$\min_{T_\theta} W_c^\phi(P_X, \hat{P}_Y) + \lambda D_{KL}(\hat{P}_Y || P_Y),$$

where W_c^ϕ is the entropy-regularized Wasserstein distance with a regularization parameter ϕ . The entropy term introduces a trade-off between transport efficiency and robustness, which is commonly observed in RD theory and IB methods.

Proposed methodology

There are several scenarios in goal-oriented SemCom, where OT and ideas from domain adaptation, transfer learning and knowledge distillation can be leveraged to address the issue of semantic misalignment. One of the baseline problems is that: We want to estimate a prediction function g in a given semantic domain \mathbf{P}_{sem} without any knowledge (or labelled sample) by exploiting the knowledge available from a source domain \mathbf{P}_S (known labeled samples) assuming there exists a non-linear transformation between the joint feature/label space distributions of the two domains \mathbf{P}_S and \mathbf{P}_{sem} that can be estimated with optimal transport. Otherwise stated, we seek to find a function f that predicts an output value given an input $x \in X$, and that minimizes the optimal transport loss between the joint source distribution \mathbf{P}_S and an estimated semantic joint distribution $\mathbf{P}_{sem}^g(X, g(X))$ depending on g .

Let $\Omega \in \mathbb{R}^d$ be a compact input measurable space of dimension d and \mathcal{C} the set of labels. Assume there is a set of data $\mathbf{X}_S = \{x_i^S\}_{i=1}^{N_S}$ associated with a set of label information $\mathbf{Y}_S = \{y_i^S\}_{i=1}^{N_S}$, $y_i^S \in \mathcal{C}$, and a data set with unknown labels $\mathbf{X}_{sem} = \{x_i^{sem}\}_{i=1}^{N_{sem}}$.

Inspired by domain adaptation, we utilize OT to align the source and target distributions by computing an optimal transport plan γ between (empirical) distributions of \mathbf{X}_S and \mathbf{X}_{sem} . Techniques such as barycentric mapping and class-wise regularization improve the accuracy of adaptation by ensuring better alignment of structures between domains. The main idea here is to address changes in both marginal and conditional distributions by aligning the joint distributions \mathbf{P}_S and \mathbf{P}_{sem} directly. Extending the Kantorovich formulation, we define the optimal coupling γ_0 as

$$\gamma_0 = \arg \min_{\gamma \in \Pi(P_S, P_{sem})} \int_{(\Omega \times C)^2} \mathcal{D}(x_1, y_1; x_2, y_2) d\gamma(x_1, y_1; x_2, y_2),$$

The cost function $\mathcal{D}(x_1, y_1; x_2, y_2) = \alpha d(x_1, x_2) + \mathcal{L}(y_1, y_2)$ combines a feature-space distance metric $d: \Omega \times \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$ with a label discrepancy function \mathcal{L} . The parameter α balances the influence of these two components. A larger α emphasizes feature alignment, while a smaller α prioritizes label alignment. In the unsupervised domain adaptation setting, semantic labels are unavailable, making direct computation of γ_0 infeasible. Instead, we approximate the target joint distribution using a function $g: \Omega \rightarrow C$ as:

$$P_{sem}^g = (x, g(x))_{x \sim \mu_{sem}}$$

where μ_{sem} is the marginal distributions over X .

Using empirical versions of P_S and P_{sem}^g , denoted by \hat{P}_S and \hat{P}_{sem}^g , respectively, we define the Wasserstein-based optimisation problem as:

$$\min_{g, \gamma} \sum_{i,j} \mathcal{D}(x_i^s, y_i^s; x_j^{sem}, g(x_j^{sem})) \gamma_{ij} = \min_g \mathcal{W}_1(\hat{P}_S, \hat{P}_{sem}^g),$$

where \mathcal{W}_1 is the 1-Wasserstein distance for the loss function $\mathcal{D}(x_1, y_1; x_2, y_2)$.

This formulation enables us to learn g by minimizing the optimal transport loss, ensuring that the predicted target labels align well with the transported source labels. The choice of α impacts the model's behaviour, with heuristic selection methods and cross-validation strategies helping to optimize performance. The current status and progress of this task involves the solution of the aforementioned optimisation problem.

Nevertheless, since other groups have also explored and worked on this problem (since proposing it in the project proposal) and its relevance - as well as the potential for novel contributions - is expected to diminish, and given that the team is focusing more on other innovative and promising approaches in goal-oriented SemCom, we do not anticipate significant advancements or novel results in domain adaptation and OT-aided approaches as the project progresses.

5.2 On the intersection of Optimal Transport and Rate-Distortion-Perception theory

Context and motivation

Rate-Distortion-Perception (RDP) theory is a recent extension of classical RD theory, aimed at optimizing lossy compression while maintaining perceptual quality. Traditional RD theory, first formulated by Shannon (1959), primarily focuses on minimizing distortion subject to a given bit rate constraint, with the assumption that distortion metrics such as mean squared error (MSE) are sufficient to quantify reconstruction quality. However, in many modern applications—including image, video, and audio compression—the human perceptual system does not evaluate quality purely based on low-level distortions but rather on high-level semantic and structural features [B71, OLK19]. This realization has motivated a shift from traditional rate-distortion objectives to perceptually-aware formulations, leading to the development of RDP theory [BM18].

A fundamental challenge in RDP theory is the lack of closed-form solutions for the rate-distortion-perception function (RDPF), particularly when dealing with continuous multivariate sources. While computational approaches have been developed for discrete sources, extending these methods to continuous sources remains difficult due to the curse of dimensionality and the complexity of high-dimensional probability distributions [BMT+19]. Existing solutions primarily rely on heuristic optimisation techniques, adversarial generative models, and perceptual loss functions, yet they often lack mathematical guarantees on optimality and convergence. Furthermore, many current implementations require large-scale data-driven training, making them unsuitable for

low-latency and resource-constrained environments, such as edge intelligence, real-time communication, and bandwidth-limited systems.

To address this gap, we present a copula-based estimation method for the RDPF, specifically in the Perfect Realism (PR) regime, under a single-letter distortion constraint. Our approach integrates output-constrained rate-distortion functions (OC-RDF) and EOT to establish a computational framework that efficiently estimates RDPF through convex optimisation. Unlike traditional methods that rely on extensive empirical tuning, our methodology leverages probabilistic copulas to model complex dependencies in continuous distributions while ensuring computational efficiency [C13, GPC18]. By formulating RDP objectives as constrained transport problems, we derive efficient parametric solutions that provide better interpretability and adaptability for high-dimensional data representations.

The proposed approach has broad implications for networked intelligent systems, SemCom, and machine learning-based compression schemes, where maintaining perceptual fidelity is crucial. In SemCom, where meaning preservation is as important as compression efficiency, RDP provides a theoretical foundation for balancing rate efficiency, semantic alignment, and user-perceived quality [SCK+21]. Additionally, in machine learning-based compression, such as deep generative models for learned compression [BLS18], our method can improve the robustness and adaptability of models to varied data distributions and task-specific constraints. By bridging Rate-Distortion theory, Perception modelling, and Optimal Transport, our work establishes a principled framework for next-generation compression and semantic-aware transmission systems.

System model and problem statement

The system model considers a multivariate continuous source subject to a single-letter distortion constraint. The main elements of the model are:

- Source Distribution: A multivariate continuous random variable X with probability density function (pdf) $f_X(x)$.
- Reconstruction Distribution: A multivariate random variable Y that aims to approximate X while satisfying perceptual constraints.
- Distortion Constraint: A function $\Delta(X, Y)$ that quantifies the difference between X and Y , ensuring that the expected distortion $E[\Delta(X, Y)]$ is within a given threshold D .
- Perceptual Constraint: A divergence measure (e.g., KL-divergence) between the source and reconstructed distributions, ensuring perceptual realism.

The problem is mathematically formulated as finding the optimal trade-off between compression rate, distortion, and perceptual quality:

$$R_{PR}(D) = \min_{f_{Y|X} \in \Pi} I(X, Y), \quad s. t., E[\Delta(X, Y)] \leq D,$$

where $I(X, Y)$ is the mutual information and Π represents the feasible set of Markov kernels satisfying the constraints.

Proposed methodology and solution

To effectively address the semantic mismatch in goal-oriented communication, we leverage the relationship between OC-RDF and EOT. This connection allows us to reformulate the OC-RDF problem as an optimisation problem within the EOT framework, enabling more efficient computational techniques. A key insight in our approach is that solving the OC-RDF problem under specific conditions is equivalent to solving an EOT problem. This equivalence enables the use of well-established optimal transport methods to tackle rate-distortion problems in a principled and computationally efficient manner.

To further simplify the problem, we introduce copula distributions, which separate the marginal distributions from the dependency structure of the source and reconstructed signals. This transformation allows us to represent the OC-RDF problem as an I-projection problem in information geometry, enhancing its analytical tractability. By employing Sklar's Theorem, we rewrite the OC-RDF problem in terms of copula functions, which provide a flexible way to model the dependence between transmitted and received signals. This enables a structured optimisation formulation where the optimal transport mapping is obtained by minimizing the KL divergence between the true and estimated distributions.

Through this formulation, we derive a convex projection-based solution, where the optimal transport map is determined as a function of specific Lagrange multipliers. The copula-based approach ensures that the dependency structure is explicitly modelled, allowing for more accurate and adaptive transmission strategies in SemCom. While the copula-based reformulation improves theoretical clarity, direct computation of the OC-RDF solution remains challenging due to high-dimensional dependencies. To address this, we develop a stochastic gradient descent-based iterative algorithm that refines the transport map through Monte Carlo sampling. The details of the algorithm can be referred to [SSK24].

By integrating the copula-based optimal transport framework, our methodology offers a principled approach to addressing goal-oriented mismatches by directly optimizing information transport. The use of stochastic optimisation and sampling-based learning ensures both scalability and computational efficiency, making it well-suited for high-dimensional SemCom tasks. Moreover, this approach enhances the robustness of 6G SemCom networks by allowing dynamic adaptation to varying data dependencies, ensuring more reliable and efficient transmission strategies. Ultimately, this framework paves the way for next-generation intelligent communication systems, where adaptive transport maps seamlessly align sender and receiver representations, optimizing both transmission efficiency and semantic fidelity.

Results

To validate the effectiveness of the proposed copula-based estimation method, we conducted numerical experiments comparing the OC-RDF solution with existing rate-distortion approaches. The results are shown in Figure 5-1 and Figure 5-2.

According to the results, the copula-based model achieves a tighter bound on the rate-distortion function compared to traditional methods, demonstrating improved approximation accuracy. Additionally, the stochastic gradient descent-based algorithm exhibits fast convergence, efficiently optimizing the transport map even under limited computational resources. Furthermore, the copula-based approach remains robust to varying channel conditions, ensuring stable performance across different network environments, making it particularly well-suited for goal-oriented 6G communication.

Conclusions

We present a novel copula-based computational framework for estimating the PR-RDPF for multivariate continuous sources under a single-letter distortion constraint. By establishing a mathematical connection between OC-RDF and EOT, we reformulate the problem as an I-projection in the KL-divergence geometry, allowing for a parametric closed-form solution. Using copula theory, we decouple the dependency structure from the marginals, leading to a convex optimisation approach that is efficiently solvable using stochastic gradient descent. The proposed method is validated through extensive numerical experiments, demonstrating its accuracy and robustness across different source distributions and distortion metrics. These findings have significant implications for lossy compression, SemCom, and perceptual coding, where maintaining a balance between distortion and perceptual quality is crucial.

Figure 5-1 PR-RDPF for various source distributions under (a) MSE distortion and (b) MAE distortion metrics.

Figure 5-2 PR-RDPF under MSE distortion metric for a (a) Gaussian, and (b) exponential bivariate source.

6 Conclusions

The 6G-GOALS framework integrates communication, computation, control, and intelligence, moving beyond traditional data transmission toward a goal-oriented and SemCom paradigm. It challenges the conventional content-blind transmission approach, emphasizing that information is valuable only when it has practical significance for the receiver. This ensures that transmitted data is relevant, context-aware, and aligned with the receiver’s learning or decision-making needs. A key challenge in SemCom is semantic mismatch, which occurs when agents use different languages, models, or representations. This can introduce semantic noise, disrupting optimized coding strategies and causing performance degradation. To address these challenges, the 6G-GOALS project explores various solutions to mitigate semantic misalignments in multi-user SemCom, proposing in this deliverable, different advancements in 6G-networks and novel AI-driven techniques.

A DeepJSCC scheme is proposed as solution for channel denoising and diffusion denoising, integrating a semantic-guided diffusion model, to counteract **data mismatch**.

Several techniques facing the **language mismatch** are then introduced. A novel technique to detect and correct discrepancies between transmitted and received meanings is proposed, leveraging the Gaussian process-based method and a human-in-the-loop reinforcement learning approach. The language mismatch in SemCom is then addressed, introducing a novel mathematical model for errors at semantic and effectiveness level, solved through an equalization algorithm based on optimal transport theory. A novel contribution highlights the impact of semantic space partitioning on semantic channel equalization, introducing a soft partitioning of the latent space to achieve more structured partitions, enhancing communication robustness.

Furthermore, two different advantages are proposed, relying on **relative representation** methods. First, a robust framework for zero-shot semantic channel equalization is presented by framing RRs within the context of frame theory, where prototypical anchors are employed as task-oriented support selection mechanism. Then, a SCE algorithm based on relative representations is introduced, enabling a receiver to decode messages from an independently trained transmitter by exchanging only a small set of data points known as anchors.

A novel framework for **latent space alignment** in MIMO SemCom is proposed, addressing the challenges posed by both semantic mismatch and channel distortions. The innovative solution integrates semantic compression with the alignment of semantic spaces through joint optimisation of MIMO semantic precoding and decoding, ensuring robust and efficient transmission.

Finally, the deliverable investigates the theoretical and practical aspects of **goal/beliefs mismatches** in SemCom networks. The proposed advanced methods aim to bridge these gaps by leveraging advanced techniques such as optimal transport for domain adaptation, and rate-distortion-perception theory, by integrating them, to develop adaptive frameworks that align mismatched knowledge representations, ensuring more robust and context-aware SemCom.

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